

Actual checklist of Tardigrada species (2009-2025 2026, 45th Edition: 18-06-2026)

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Introduction

More than one thousand Tardigrada species were included in the published checklist (Guidetti, R. & Bertolani, R. 2005. Tardigrade taxonomy: an updated check list of the taxa and a list of characters for their identification. *Zootaxa*, 845, 1–46.) plus the additions and corrections to this checklist (Degma, P. & Guidetti, R. 2007. Notes to the current checklist of Tardigrada. *Zootaxa*, 1579, 41–53.). For practical reasons, we have joined these two papers (without comments added to particular taxa as well as without references published in these papers) into an accurate combined version of the checklists. We incorporated all taxonomical novelties in the current edition of the Checklist even if they were published just online. Then, following the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature, we corrected the year of a taxon description in its print edition. This checklist is free for all users, but utilization of it requires the citation of the two original papers. This checklist is the platform for occasional upgrades (date of latest upgrade is in the title). The changings respect to the previous version of the checklist have yellow background.

If you also use these changes, please also cite this checklist (Degma, P. & Guidetti, R. 2026. Actual checklist of Tardigrada species. 45th Edition. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20746849. Accessed ~~date~~).

Previous versions of the checklist are available at the following DOI: 10.25431/11380_1178608.

This checklist collects the taxonomic and systematic information available in the bibliography, so the authors do not necessarily share what is reported in the articles used for the composition of this list.

Currently there are 35 families, 164 168 genera, 1511 1549 species and 16 additional subspecies/forms included in the checklist.

Please write us if you find any mistake or missing data in this checklist. Your help in its improvement will be acknowledged.

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Checklist of Tardigrada

(The assignment of synonyms are reported within square parenthesis ‘ [] ’. Amendments and changes of taxa are reported within angle brackets ‘ < > ’. Comments are reported within brace parenthesis ‘ { } ’. The species written in bold characters are the genus *type species*)

Phylum: TARDIGRADA Doyère, 1840

Class: HETEROTARDIGRADA Marcus, 1927 {2 orders}

Order: ARTHROTARDIGRADA Marcus, 1927 {11 families}
<Order invalid according to Grollmann *et al.* 2023>

Family: Anisonychidae Møbjerg, Jørgensen & Kristensen, 2020 {1 genus}

Anisonyches Pollock, 1975 {4 species}

<Amended by Bartels *et al.* 2018>

<Amended and transferred from Echiniscoididae by Møbjerg *et al.* 2020>

Anisonyches deliquus Chang & Rho, 1998

Anisonyches diakidius Pollock, 1975 <Amended by Bartels *et al.* 2018>

Anisonyches eleutherensis Bartels, Fontoura & Nelson, 2018

Anisonyches mauritanus Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia & Daddabbo,

1987

Family: Archechiniscidae Binda, 1978 {1 genus}
[Archechiniscinae in Grimaldi de Zio & D'Addabbo Gallo, 1987]
{Jørgensen *et al.* 2010 reconsider valid the family}

Archechiniscus Schulz, 1953 {6 species}
Archechiniscus bahamensis Bartels, Fontoura & Nelson, 2018
Archechiniscus biscaynei Miller, Clark & C. Miller, 2012
Archechiniscus marci Schulz, 1953
Archechiniscus minutus Grimaldi de Zio & D'Addabbo Gallo, 1987
Archechiniscus murilloi Bartels & Fontoura, 2021 {in Bartels *et al.* 2021}
Archechiniscus symbalanus Chang & Rho, 1998

Family: Batillipedidae Ramazzotti, 1962 {1 genus}
<Amended by Gallo D'Addabbo *et al.* 2005>
[Discopodidae Marcus, 1934]

Batillipes Richters, 1909 {41 43 species}
Batillipes acaudatus Pollock, 1971
Batillipes acuticauda Menechella, Bulnes & Cazzaniga, 2015
Batillipes adriaticus Grimaldi de Zio, Morone De Lucia, D'Addabbo Gallo & Grimaldi, 1979
Batillipes africanus Morone De Lucia, D'Addabbo Gallo & Grimaldi de Zio, 1988
Batillipes algharbensis E. Santos, Rubal, Veiga, da Rocha & Fontoura, 2018
Batillipes amblypyge Menechella, Bulnes & Cazzaniga, 2017
Batillipes annulatus de Zio, 1962
Batillipes brasiliensis E. Santos, da Rocha, Gomes Jr. & Fontoura, 2017
Batillipes bullacaudatus McGinty & Higgins, 1968
Batillipes carnonensis Fize, 1957
Batillipes chandrayaani Vishnudattan, Rubal & Bijoy Nandan, 2024
Batillipes crassipes Tchesunov & Mokievsky, 1995
Batillipes dandarae E. Santos, da Rocha, Gomes Jr. & Fontoura, 2017
Batillipes dicrocercus Pollock, 1970
Batillipes friaufi Riggan, 1962
Batillipes gilmartini McGinty, 1969
Batillipes homocercus Bartels & Fontoura, 2021 {in Bartels *et al.* 2021}
Batillipes ichthyocercus Bartels & Fontoura, 2021 {in Bartels *et al.* 2021}
Batillipes kalami Vishnudattan, Rubal & Bijoy Nandan, 2023
Batillipes lesteri Kristensen & Mackness, 2000
Batillipes lingularum Menechella, Bulnes & Cazzaniga, 2017
Batillipes littoralis Renaud-Debyser, 1959
Batillipes longispinosus Chang & Rho, 1997
Batillipes lusitanus Santos, Rubal, Veiga, da Rocha & Fontoura, 2018
***Batillipes malaysianus* C.-A. Chen & Ng, 2025 {in Chen *et al.* 2025}**
Batillipes marcelli Morone De Lucia, D'Addabbo Gallo & Grimaldi de Zio, 1988
Batillipes minius Rubal, Veiga, Fontoura & Sousa-Pinto, 2016

Batillipes mirus Richters, 1909 [*Batillipes caudatus* Hay, 1917]
Batillipes nioensis Vishnudattan, Rubal & Kalyan De, 2025
Batillipes noerrevangi Kristensen, 1978
Batillipes orientalis Chang & Rho, 1997
Batillipes pennaki Marcus, 1946
Batillipes philippinensis Chang & Rho, 1997
Batillipes phreaticus Renaud Debyser, 1959 [*Batillipes littoralis submersus* D'Hondt, 1970]
Batillipes potiguarensis E. Santos, da Rocha, Gomes Jr. & Fontoura, 2017
Batillipes roscoffensis Kristensen, 1978
Batillipes rotundiculus Rho & Chang, 1999 {in Rho *et al.* 1999}
Batillipes similis Schulz, 1955
Batillipes solitarius Jørgensen, Boesgaard, Møbjerg & Kristensen, 2014
Batillipes spinicauda Gallo D'Addabbo, Sandulli & de Zio Grimaldi, 2005
Batillipes tridentatus Pollock, 1989
Batillipes tubernatis Pollock, 1971
Batillipes wyedeleinorum Bartels, Fontoura, Nelson & Kaczmarek, 2024

Family: Coronarctidae Renaud-Mornant, 1974 {2 genera}
<Amended by Hansen 2007>

Coronarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1974 {~~11~~ 12 species}
<Amended by Hansen 2007>

Coronarctus disparilis Renaud-Mornant, 1987
Coronarctus dissimilis Gomes-Júnior, E. Santos, da Rocha, P.J.P. Santos & Fontoura, 2020
Coronarctus fastigatus Renaud-Mornant, 1987
Coronarctus laubieri Renaud-Mornant, 1987
Coronarctus mexicus Romano III, Gallo, D'Addabbo, Accogli, Baguley & Montagna, 2011
Coronarctus neptunus Gomes-Júnior, E. Santos, da Rocha, P.J.P. Santos & Fontoura, 2020
Coronarctus sonne Saulenko, Maiorova, Martínez Arbizu & Mordukhovich, 2022
Coronarctus stylisetus Renaud-Mornant, 1987
Coronarctus tenellus Renaud-Mornant, 1974
Coronarctus verrucatus Hansen, 2007
Coronarctus xiximii Delgado-Reyes, Armendariz-Toledano, Montiel-Parra, Rocha-Olivares & Rivas, 2026
Coronarctus yurupari Gomes-Júnior, E. Santos, da Rocha, P.J.P. Santos & Fontoura, 2020

Trogloarctus Villora-Moreno, 1996 {1 species}
Trogloarctus trionyches Villora-Moreno, 1996

Family: Halechiniscidae Thulin, 1928 {6 subfamilies}
<Amended by Fujimoto *et al.* 2017>

Subfamily: Dipodarctinae Pollock, 1995 {1 genus}
<Amended by Jørgensen *et al.* 2014>

Dipodarctus Pollock, 1995 {5 species}

<Amended by Jørgensen *et al.* 2014>

Dipodarctus anaholiensis Pollock, 1995

Dipodarctus australiensis Jørgensen, Boesgaard, Møbjerg & Kristensen, 2014

Dipodarctus borrori Pollock, 1995 [*Hemitanarctus chimaera* de Zio Grimaldi, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia & Troccoli, 1995/96 according to de Zio Grimaldi *et al.* 2003]

Dipodarctus subterraneus (Renaud-Debyser, 1959)

Dipodarctus susannae Jørgensen, Boesgaard, Møbjerg & Kristensen, 2014

Subfamily: Euclavarctinae Renaud-Mornant, 1983 {6 7 genera}

Clavarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1983 {1 species}

Clavarctus falculus Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Euclavarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1975 {2 species}

<Amended by Renaud-Mornant 1983>

Euclavarctus convergens Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Euclavarctus thieli Renaud-Mornant, 1975

Exoclavarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1983 {1 species}

Exoclavarctus dineti Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Moebjergarctus Bussau, 1992 {3 species}

Moebjergarctus clarionclippertonensis Bai, X. Wang, Zhou, Lin, Meng & Fontoura, 2020

Moebjergarctus manganis Bussau, 1992

Moebjergarctus okhotensis Saulenko, Maiorova, Martínez Arbizu & Mordukhovich, 2022

Parmursa Renaud-Mornant, 1984 {2 species}

<Amended by Hansen 2007>

Parmursa fimbriata Renaud-Mornant, 1984

Parmursa torquata Hansen, 2007

Proclavarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1983 {1 species}

Proclavarctus fragilis Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Ranarctus Fujimoto, Yamasaki & Ohtsuka, 2026 {1 species}

Ranarctus kondoi Fujimoto, Yamasaki & Ohtsuka, 2026

Subfamily: Florarctinae Renaud-Mornant, 1982 {4 genera}

<Amended by Kristensen 1984 and Hansen & Kristensen 2021>

Florarctus Delamare Deboutteville & Renaud-Mornant, 1965 {15 species}

Florarctus acer Renaud-Mornant, 1989

Florarctus antillensis Van der Land, 1968

Florarctus asper Renaud-Mornant, 1989

Florarctus bellahelenae Gąsiorek, D. Kristensen & Kristensen, 2021

Florarctus cinctus Renaud-Mornant, 1976

Florarctus glareolus Noda, 1987
Florarctus heimi Delamare Deboutteville & Renaud-Mornant, 1965 [*Florarctus cervinus*
Renaud-Mornant, 1987 according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021a]
Florarctus hulingsi Renaud-Mornant, 1976
Florarctus kwoni Chang & Rho, 1997
Florarctus pulcher Grimaldi de Zio, Lamarca, D'addabbo Gallo & Pietanza, 1999
Florarctus salvati Delamare Deboutteville & Renaud-Mornant, 1965
Florarctus stellatus Renaud-Mornant, 1989
Florarctus vulcanius Renaud-Mornant, 1987
Florarctus wunai Fujimoto, 2015
Florarctus yucatanensis Anguas-Escalante, de Jesus-Navarrete, DeMilio, Pérez-Pech & Hansen,
2020

Higginsarctus Hansen & Kristensen, 2021 {6 species}
Higginsarctus alatus (Gomes-Júnior, E. Santos, da Rocha, P.J.P. Santos & Fontoura, 2018)
<Transferred from *Ligiarctus* by Hansen & Kristensen 2021>
Higginsarctus lassei Hansen & Kristensen, 2021
Higginsarctus laurae Hansen & Kristensen, 2021
Higginsarctus martini Hansen & Kristensen, 2021
Higginsarctusshintai Hansen & Kristensen, 2021
Higginsarctus signeae Hansen & Kristensen, 2021

Ligiarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1982 {1 species}
<Amended by Gomes-Júnior *et al.* 2018 and Hansen & Kristensen 2021>
Ligiarctus eastwardi Renaud-Mornant, 1982

Wingstrandarctus Kristensen, 1984 {5 species}
Wingstrandarctus corallinus Kristensen, 1984
Wingstrandarctus crypticus Renaud-Mornant, 1989
Wingstrandarctus intermedius (Renaud-Mornant, 1967) <Amended by Renaud-Mornant 1989>
Wingstrandarctus stinae Jørgensen, Boesgaard, Møbjerg & Kristensen, 2014
Wingstrandarctus unsculptus Jørgensen, Boesgaard, Møbjerg & Kristensen, 2014

Subfamily: Halechiniscinae Thulin, 1928 {2 genera}
<Amended by Grimaldi de Zio *et al.* 1990>

Chrysoarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1984 {2 species}
Chrysoarctus briandi Renaud-Mornant, 1984
Chrysoarctus flabellatus (Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia, Vaccarella &
Grimaldi, 1982)

Halechiniscus Richters, 1908 {12 species + 1 subspecies}
Halechiniscus chafarinensis Grimaldi de Zio & Villora Moreno, 1995
Halechiniscus churakaagii Fujimoto, 2015
Halechiniscus greveni Renaud-Mornant & Deroux, 1976
Halechiniscus guiteli Richters, 1908

Halechiniscus janus Bai, X. Wang, Gao, Y. Li & Fontoura, 2022
Halechiniscus jejuensis Chang & Rho, 2002
Halechiniscus macrocephalus Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1988
Halechiniscus paratuleari Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1988
Halechiniscus perfectus Schulz, 1955
Halechiniscus remanei remanei Schulz, 1955
Halechiniscus remanei antillensis Renaud-Mornant, 1984
Halechiniscus tuleari Renaud-Mornant, 1979
Halechiniscus yanakaagii Fujimoto, 2015

Subfamily: Orzeliscinae Schulz, 1963 {4 genera}
<Amended by Gross *et al.* 2014>

Mutaparadoxipus Gross, Miller & Hochberg, 2014 {1 species}
Mutaparadoxipus duodigifinis Gross, Miller & Hochberg, 2014

Opydorscus Renaud-Mornant, 1989 {1 species}
Opydorscus fonsecae Renaud-Mornant, 1989

Orzeliscus du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1952 {2 species}
Orzeliscus asiaticus J.M. Lee, Rho & Chang, 2017
Orzeliscus belopus du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1952 [*Orzeliscus septentrionalis* Schulz, 1953
according to Pollock 1982]

Paradoxipus Kristensen & Higgins, 1989 {1 species}
<Transferred from Halechiniscinae by Gross *et al.* 2014>
Paradoxipus orzeliscoides Kristensen & Higgins, 1989

Subfamily: Quisarctinae Fujimoto, 2015 {1 genus}
<Amended by Trokhymchuk *et al.* 2025>

Quisarctus Fujimoto, 2015 {1 2 species}
<Amended by Trokhymchuk *et al.* 2025>
Quisarctus armatus Trokhymchuk, Martínez Arbizu, Kristensen & Kieneke, 2025
Quisarctus yasumurai Fujimoto, 2015

Family: Neoarctidae (de Zio Grimaldi, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1992) {1 genus}
<Former subfamily of Stygarctidae elevated to family level and amended by Bello & Grimaldi de
Zio 1998>

Neoarctus de Zio Grimaldi, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1992 {1 species}
Neoarctus primigenius de Zio Grimaldi, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1992

Family: Neostygarctidae Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo & De Lucia Morone, 1987 {1
genus}
{Not more valid according to Hansen *et al.* 2012, Fontoura *et al.* 2017 and Tchesunov 2018;

Considered valid and amended by Fujimoto & Miyazaki 2013 (however the authors were not aware of Hansen *et al.* 2012 publication); Amended by Kristensen *et al.* 2015}

Neostygarctus Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1982 {4 species}
<Transferred to Renaudarctidae by Kristensen & Higgins 1984b; Elevated to family level and amended by Grimaldi de Zio *et al.* 1987; Transferred from Neostygarctidae into Stygarctidae by Hansen *et al.* 2012; Re-transferred by Kristensen *et al.* 2015>

Neostygarctus acanthophorus Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1982

Neostygarctus grossmeteori Tchesunov, 2018

Neostygarctus lovedeluxe Fujimoto & Miyazaki, 2013 {Species described in Neostygarctidae by Fujimoto & Miyazaki 2013}

Neostygarctus oceanopolis Kristensen, Sørensen, Hansen & Zeppilli, 2015

Family: Renaudarctidae Kristensen & Higgins, 1984 {2 genera}
<Amended by Hansen *et al.* 2012 and by Fujimoto & Yamasaki 2017>

Nodarctus Fujimoto & Yamasaki, 2017 {1 species}

Nodarctus hallucis Fujimoto & Yamasaki, 2017

Renaudarctus Kristensen & Higgins, 1984 {2 species}

<Amended by Hansen *et al.* 2012>

Renaudarctus fossorius Hansen, Kristensen & Jørgensen, 2012

Renaudarctus psammocryptus Kristensen & Higgins, 1984

Family: Stygarctidae Schulz, 1951 {2 subfamilies}

<Amended by Hansen *et al.* 2012>

Subfamily: Megastygarctidinae Bello & de Zio Grimaldi, 1998 {1 genus}

<Amended by Hansen & Kristensen 2006>

Megastygarctides McKirdy, Schmidt & McGinty-Bayly, 1976 {6 species}

Megastygarctides christinae Hansen & Kristensen, 2006

Megastygarctides gerdae Hansen & Kristensen, 2006

Megastygarctides isounguis Renaud-Mornant, 1981

Megastygarctides orbiculatus McKirdy, Schmidt & McGinty-Bayly, 1976

Megastygarctides setoloso Morgan & O'Reilly, 1989

Megastygarctides sezginii Ürkmez, Ostrowska, Roszkowska, Gawlak, Zawierucha, Kristensen & Kaczmarek, 2017

Subfamily: Stygarctinae Schulz, 1951 {7 genera}

Faroestygarctus Hansen, Kristensen & Jørgensen, 2012 {1 species}

Faroestygarctus dezioae Hansen, Kristensen & Jørgensen, 2012

Hansenarctus Fujimoto & Ohtsuka, 2019 {1 species}

Hansenarctus toyoshiomaruae Fujimoto & Ohtsuka, 2019

Mesostygarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1979 {2 species}

<Amended and reconsidered valid as genus by Hansen *et al.* 2012>

Mesostygarctus intermedius Renaud-Mornant, 1979 <Transferred from *Pseudostygarctus* by Hansen *et al.* 2012>

Mesostygarctus spiralis Hansen, Kristensen & Jørgensen, 2012

Parastygarctus Renaud-Debyser, 1965 {7 species}

<Amended by Hansen *et al.* 2012>

Parastygarctus biungulatus Morone De Lucia, Grimaldi de Zio & D'Addabbo Gallo, 1984

Parastygarctus higginsi Renaud-Debyser, 1965

Parastygarctus mediterranicus Gallo D'Addabbo, Grimaldi de Zio & Sandulli, 2001

Parastygarctus renaudae Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia & Daddabbo, 1987

Parastygarctus robustus Hansen, Kristensen & Jørgensen, 2012

Parastygarctus sterreri Renaud-Mornant, 1970

Parastygarctus svennevigi Hansen, Kristensen & Jørgensen, 2012

Prostygarctus Rubal, Veiga, Fontoura & Sousa-Pinto, 2013 {1 species}

Prostygarctus aculeatus Rubal, Veiga, Fontoura & Sousa-Pinto, 2013

Pseudostygarctus McKirdy, Schmidt & McGinty-Bayly, 1976 {5 species}

<Amended by Hansen *et al.* 2012>

Pseudostygarctus apuliae Gallo D'Addabbo, de Zio Grimaldi & D'Addabbo, 2000

Pseudostygarctus galloae Hansen, Kristensen & Jørgensen, 2012

Pseudostygarctus mirabilis de Zio Grimaldi, D'Addabbo Gallo & Morone De Lucia, 1998

Pseudostygarctus rugosus Gallo D'Addabbo, de Zio Grimaldi & Sandulli, 2001

Pseudostygarctus triungulatus McKirdy, Schmidt & McGinty-Bayly, 1976 <Amended by Hansen *et al.* 2012>

Stygarctus Schulz, 1951 {8 species}

Stygarctus abornatus McKirdy, Schmidt & McGinty-Bayly, 1976

Stygarctus ayatori Fujimoto, 2014

Stygarctus bradypus Schulz, 1951

Stygarctus goubaultae Renaud-Mornant, 1981

Stygarctus granulatus Pollock, 1970

Stygarctus keralensis Vishnudattan, Bijoy Nandan, Hansen & Jayachandran, 2021

Stygarctus lambertii Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia & Daddabbo, 1987

Stygarctus spinifer Hiruta, 1985

Family: Styraconyxidae Kristensen & Renaud-Mornant, 1983 {11 genera}

<Amended by Jørgensen *et al.* 2014; Former subfamily of Halechiniscidae elevated to family level and amended by Fujimoto *et al.* 2017>

Angursa Pollock, 1979 {9 species}

<Amended by Fujimoto & Hansen 2019 and Tchesunov & Fedyaeva 2024>

Angursa abyssalis Renaud-Mornant, 1981 <Amended by Fujimoto & Hansen 2019 who consider *Angursa bicuspis abyssalis* to be a valid species> {For taxonomic status of of the subspecies see Kaczmarek *et al.* 2015}
Angursa antarctica Villora-Moreno, 1998 <Amended by Fujimoto & Hansen 2019>
Angursa bicuspis Pollock, 1979 <Amended by Fujimoto & Hansen 2019>
Angursa capsula Bussau, 1992
Angursa clavifera Noda, 1985 <*A. bicuspis clavifera* elevated to species level by Bussau 1992>
Angursa lanceolata Renaud-Mornant, 1981 <Amended by Fujimoto & Hansen 2019>
Angursa lingua Bussau, 1992
Angursa olenevskii Tchesunov & Fedyaeva, 2024
Angursa seisumaruae Fujimoto & Hansen, 2019

Bathyechiniscus Steiner, 1926 {1 species}
Bathyechiniscus tetronyx Steiner, 1926 <Amended by Pollock 1983>

Cyaegharctus Fujimoto & Jimi, 2020 {1 species}
Cyaegharctus kitamurai Fujimoto & Jimi, 2020

Lepoarctus Kristensen & Renaud-Mornant, 1983 {1 species}
Lepoarctus coniferus (Renaud-Mornant, 1975)

Paratanarctus D'Addabbo Gallo, Grimaldi de Zio, Morone De Lucia & Troccoli, 1992 {1 species}
Paratanarctus kristenseni D'Addabbo Gallo, Grimaldi de Zio, Morone De Lucia & Troccoli, 1992

Pleocola Cantacuzène, 1951 {1 species}
Pleocola limnoriae Cantacuzène, 1951

Raiarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1981 {5 species}
<Amended by Jørgensen *et al.* 2014>
Raiarctus aureolatus Renaud-Mornant, 1981
Raiarctus colurus Renaud-Mornant, 1981
Raiarctus jesperii Jørgensen, Boesgaard, Møbjerg & Kristensen, 2014
Raiarctus katrinae Jørgensen, Boesgaard, Møbjerg & Kristensen, 2014
Raiarctus variabilis D'Addabbo Gallo, Grimaldi de Zio & Morone De Lucia, 1986

Rhomboarctus Renaud-Mornant, 1984 {3 species}
Rhomboarctus aslaki Hansen, Gallo D'Addabbo & de Zio Grimaldi, 2003
Rhomboarctus duplicicaudatus Hansen, Gallo D'Addabbo & de Zio Grimaldi, 2003
Rhomboarctus thomassini Renaud-Mornant, 1984

Styraconyx Thulin, 1942 {16 species + 1 subspecies}
Styraconyx craticuliformis Chang & Rho, 1998
Styraconyx craticulus (Pollock, 1983)
Styraconyx hallasi Kristensen, 1977

Styraconyx haploceros Thulin, 1942
Styraconyx kristenseni kristenseni Renaud-Mornant, 1981
Styraconyx kristenseni neocaledonensis Renaud-Mornant, 1981
Styraconyx nanoqsunguak Kristensen & Higgins, 1984
Styraconyx paulae Robotti, 1971
Styraconyx qivitoq Kristensen & Higgins, 1984
Styraconyx robertoi Pérez-Pech, de Jesús-Navarrate, DeMilio, Anguas-Escalante & Hansen, 2020
Styraconyx sardiniae D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia & Grimaldi de Zio, 1989
Styraconyx sargassi Thulin, 1942
Styraconyx takeshii Fujimoto, Suzuki, Ito, Tamura & Tsujimoto, 2020
Styraconyx testudo D'Addabbo Gallo, Grimaldi de Zio & Morone De Lucia, 1984
Styraconyx turbinarium Bartels, Fontoura & Nelson, 2015
Styraconyx tyrrhenus D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia & Grimaldi de Zio, 1989
Styraconyx vargasi Bartels & Fontoura, 2021 {in Bartels *et al.* 2021}

Tetrakentron Cuénot, 1892 {1 species}

Tetrakentron synaptae Cuénot, 1892

Tholoarctus Kristensen & Renaud-Mornant, 1983 {2 species + 1 subspecies}
<Amended by Jørgensen *et al.* 2014>

Tholoarctus natans natans Kristensen & Renaud-Mornant, 1983

Tholoarctus natans pedunculatus D'Addabbo Gallo, de Zio Grimaldi, Morone De Lucia & Troccoli, 1992

Tholoarctus oleseni Jørgensen, Boesgaard, Møbjerg & Kristensen, 2014

Family: Tanarctidae Renaud-Mornant, 1980 {3 genera}

<Former subfamily of Halechiniscidae elevated to family level and amended by Fujimoto *et al.* 2017>

Actinarctus Schulz, 1935 {4 5 species + 1 subspecies}

Actinarctus doryphorus doryphorus Schulz, 1935

Actinarctus doryphorus ocellatus Renaud-Mornant, 1971

Actinarctus lyrophorus Renaud-Mornant, 1979

Actinarctus neretinus Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia, Vaccarella & Grimaldi, 1982

Actinarctus odissi Vishnudattan, Rubal & De, 2026

Actinarctus physophorus Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia, Vaccarella & Grimaldi, 1982

Tanarctus Renaud-Debyser, 1959 {15 species}

Tanarctus arbor-spinosus Lindgren, 1971

Tanarctus breedyae Bartels & Fontoura, 2021 {in Bartels *et al.* 2021}

Tanarctus bubulubus Jørgensen & Kristensen, 2001

Tanarctus dendriticus Renaud-Mornant, 1980

Tanarctus diplocerus Fujimoto, Miyazaki & Suzuki, 2013

Tanarctus gracilis Renaud-Mornant, 1980

Tanarctus helleouetae Renaud-Mornant, 1984
Tanarctus heterodactylus Renaud-Mornant, 1980
Tanarctus hirsutospinosus Jørgensen, Boesgaard, Møbjerg & Kristensen, 2014
Tanarctus ittanmomen Fujimoto, 2018
Tanarctus longisetosus Grimaldi de Zio, D'Addabbo Gallo, Morone De Lucia, Vaccarella & Grimaldi, 1982
Tanarctus minotauricus Renaud-Mornant, 1984
Tanarctus ramazzottii Renaud-Mornant, 1975
Tanarctus tauricus Renaud-Debyser, 1959
Tanarctus velatus McKirdy, Schmidt & McGinty-Bayly, 1976

Zioella Renaud-Mornant, 1987 {1 species}

Zioella pavonina Renaud-Mornant, 1987

Order: ECHINISCOIDEA Richters, 1926 {4 families}

Family: Echiniscoididae Kristensen & Hallas, 1980 {2 subfamilies}
<Amended by Møbjerg *et al.* 2020>

Subfamily: Echiniscoidinae Kristensen & Hallas, 1980 {2 genera}
<Amended by Møbjerg *et al.* 2020>

Echiniscoides Plate, 1888 {~~21~~ 22 species}

Echiniscoides andamanensis Chang & Rho, 1998
Echiniscoides basalticus Gąsiorek & Kristensen, 2022
Echiniscoides bruni D'Addabbo Gallo, Grimaldi de Zio, Morone De Lucia & Troccoli, 1992
Echiniscoides bufocephalus Gąsiorek & Kristensen, 2022
Echiniscoides costaricensis Bartels & Fontoura, 2021 {in Bartels *et al.* 2021}
Echiniscoides galliensis Kristensen & Hallas, 1980 <*E. sigismundi galliensis* elevated to species level by Gąsiorek & Kristensen 2022>
Echiniscoides groenlandicus Kristensen & Hallas, 1980 <*E. sigismundi groenlandicus* elevated to species level by Gąsiorek & Kristensen 2022>
Echiniscoides hispaniensis Kristensen & Hallas, 1980 <*E. sigismundi hispaniensis* elevated to species level and amended by Gąsiorek & Kristensen 2022>
Echiniscoides hoepneri Kristensen & Hallas, 1980
Echiniscoides lichenophilus Gąsiorek & Kristensen, 2022
Echiniscoides mediterranicus Kristensen & Hallas, 1980 <*E. sigismundi mediterranicus* elevated to species level by Gąsiorek & Kristensen 2022>
Echiniscoides musa Gąsiorek & Kristensen, 2022
Echiniscoides polynesiensis Renaud-Mornant, 1976 <*E. sigismundi polynesiensis* elevated to species level by Gąsiorek & Kristensen 2022>
Echiniscoides porphyrae Grimaldi de Zio, Gallo D'Addabbo & Pietanza, 2000 <*E. sigismundi porphyrae* elevated to species level by Gąsiorek & Kristensen 2022>
Echiniscoides ritavargasae Bartels, Fontoura, Mioduchowska & Kaczmarek, 2021 {in Bartels *et al.* 2021}
Echiniscoides rugostellatus Perry, Rawson, Ameral, Miller, J.D. Miller, 2018

Echiniscoides sigismundi (M. Schultze, 1865)

Echiniscoides testudolapis Kihm, Gąsiorek, Rho, H. Lee, Han, Kim, Kang, Choi, Jung & Park, 2025

Echiniscoides travei Bellido & Bertrand, 1981

Echiniscoides trichosus Gąsiorek & Kristensen, 2022

Echiniscoides verrucariae Grimaldi de Zio, Gallo D'Addabbo & Pietanza, 2000 <*E. sigismundi* *verrucariae* elevated to species level by Gąsiorek & Kristensen 2022>

Echiniscoides wyethi Perry & Miller, 2015

Neoechiniscoides Møbjerg, Jørgensen & Kristensen, 2020 {3 species}

Neoechiniscoides aski Møbjerg, Jørgensen & Kristensen, 2020

Neoechiniscoides horningi (Miller & Kristensen, 1999) <Transferred from *Echiniscoides* by Møbjerg *et al.* 2020>

Neoechiniscoides pollocki (Hallas & Kristensen, 1982) <Transferred from *Echiniscoides* by Møbjerg *et al.* 2020>

Subfamily: Isoechiniscoidinae Møbjerg, Kristensen & Jørgensen, 2016 {1 genus}

Isoechiniscoides Møbjerg, Kristensen & Jørgensen, 2016 {2 species}

Isoechiniscoides higginsii (Hallas & Kristensen, 1982) <Transferred from *Echiniscoides* by Møbjerg *et al.* 2016>

Isoechiniscoides sifae Møbjerg, Kristensen & Jørgensen, 2016

Family: Carphanidae Binda & Kristensen, 1986 {1 genus}

Carphania Binda, 1978 {1 species}

Carphania fluviatilis Binda, 1978

Family: Oreellidae Ramazzotti, 1962 (*sensu* Puglia unpublished thesis 1959) {1 genus}
<Amended by Binda & Kristensen 1986 and Dastych *et al.* 1998>

Oreella Murray, 1910 {3 species}

Oreella chugachii Calloway, Miller, Johansson & Whiting, 2011

Oreella mollis Murray, 1910 [*Oreella minor* Ramazzotti, 1964]

Oreella vilucensis Rahm, 1931 *species inquirenda* [*Oreella bonnensis* Rahm, 1932]

Family: Echiniscidae Thulin, 1928 {22-23 genera}

{Guil *et al.* 2019 proposed subfamilies Echiniscinae Thulin, 1928, Parechiniscinae Guil, Jørgensen & Kristensen, 2019 and Pseudechiniscinae Guil, Jørgensen & Kristensen, 2019 as well as tribes Anthechiniscini Guil, Jørgensen & Kristensen, 2019, Bryodelphaxini Guil, Jørgensen & Kristensen, 2019, Cornechiniscini Guil, Jørgensen & Kristensen, 2019, Echiniscini Thulin, 1928, Novechiniscini Guil, Jørgensen & Kristensen, 2019, Parechiniscini Guil, Jørgensen & Kristensen, 2019 and Pseudechiniscini Guil, Jørgensen & Kristensen, 2019 - all these taxa were later suppressed by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020b}

Acanthechiniscus Vecchi, Cesari, Bertolani, Jönsson, Rebecchi & Guidetti, 2016 {5-4 species}

Acanthechiniscus aestivalis Kihm, Gąsiorek, Kang & Park, 2026

Acanthechiniscus distinctus (Mihelčič, 1951) <Transferred from *Pseudechiniscus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Acanthechiniscus goedeni (Grigarick, Mihelčič & Schuster, 1964) <Transferred from *Pseudechiniscus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a> {see *Polyacanthechiniscus*}

Acanthechiniscus islandicus (Richters, 1904) <Transferred from *Pseudechiniscus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a> {see *Polyacanthechiniscus*}

Acanthechiniscus sinensis (Rahm, 1937) <Transferred from *Pseudechiniscus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Acanthechiniscus victor (Ehrenberg, 1853) [*Pseudechiniscus tridentifer* Bartoš, 1935]
<Transferred from *Pseudechiniscus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Antechiniscus Kristensen, 1987 {7 species}

Antechiniscus conversus (Horning & Schuster, 1983)

Antechiniscus jermani Rossi & Claps, 1989

Antechiniscus lateromamillatus (Ramazzotti, 1964)

Antechiniscus moscali Claxton, 2001

Antechiniscus parvisentus (Horning & Schuster, 1983)

Antechiniscus perplexus (Horning & Schuster, 1983)

Antechiniscus pulcher (Murray, 1910) <Transferred from *Pseudechiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021c>

Barbaria Michalczyk, Gąsiorek, Morek & Stec, 2019 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d} {13 species}

Barbaria bigranulata (Richters, 1908) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Barbaria charrua (Claps & Rossi, 1997) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022a>

Barbaria danieli (Meyer, Tsaliki & Sorgee, 2017) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Barbaria ganczareki (Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2007) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Barbaria hanna (Roszkowska, Gawlak, Draga & Kaczmarek, 2019) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Barbaria jenningsi (Dastyh, 1984) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Barbaria madonnae (Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2006) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Barbaria ollantaytamboensis (Nickel, Miller & Marley, 2001) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Barbaria paucigranulata Wilamowski, Vončina, Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022a}

Barbaria quitensis (Pilato, 2007) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022a>

Barbaria ranzii (Ramazzotti, 1964) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Barbaria rufoviridis (du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1944) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* to

Viridiscus by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d and from *Viridiscus* to *Barbaria* by Rocha *et al.* 2023>

Barbaria weglarskae Gąsiorek, Wilamowski, Vončina & Michalczyk, 2022

Brychoerus Marcus, 1936 {2 species + 2 subspecies}

<Amended by DeMilio *et al.* 2022a>

Bryochoerus intermedius intermedius (Murray, 1910)
Bryochoerus intermedius hawaiiicus (Thulin, 1928)
Bryochoerus intermedius laevis (Marcus, 1936)
Bryochoerus liupanensis Xue, X. Li, L. Wang, Xian, H. Chen, 2017

Bryodelphax Thulin, 1928 {30 species}
<Amended by DeMilio *et al.* 2022a>

Bryodelphax aaseae Kristensen, Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2010 <Amended by DeMilio *et al.* 2022a>
Bryodelphax alzirae (du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1944)
Bryodelphax amphoterus (Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1975)
Bryodelphax arenosus Gąsiorek, 2018
Bryodelphax asiaticus Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2004
Bryodelphax atlantis Fontoura, Pilato & Lisi, 2008
Bryodelphax australasiaticus Gąsiorek, Vončina, Degma & Michalczyk, 2020
Bryodelphax beniowskii T. Bartylak, Kayastha, Roszkowska & Kaczmarek, 2022 {in Bartylak *et al.* 2022}
Bryodelphax brevidentatus Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Degma, 2005
Bryodelphax crossotus Grigarick, Schuster & Nelson, 1983
Bryodelphax decoratus Gąsiorek, Vončina, Degma & Michalczyk, 2020
Bryodelphax dominicanus (Schuster & Toftner, 1982)
Bryodelphax instabilis Gąsiorek & Degma, 2018
Bryodelphax iohannis Bertolani, Guidi & Rebecchi, 1996
Bryodelphax kristenseni Lisi, Daza, Londoño & Quiroga, 2017
Bryodelphax lijiangensis T. Yang, 2002
Bryodelphax maculatus Gąsiorek, Stec, Morek, Marnissi & Michalczyk, 2017
Bryodelphax mareki Kayastha, Roszkowska, Mioduchowska, Gawlak & Kaczmarek, 2021
Bryodelphax mateusi (Fontoura, 1982)
Bryodelphax meronensis Pilato, Lisi & Binda, 2010
Bryodelphax nigripunctatus Degma, Gąsiorek, Vončina & Michalczyk, 2020 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2020}
Bryodelphax olszanowskii Kaczmarek, Parnikoza, Gawlak, Esefeld, Peter, Kozeretska & Roszkowska, 2018
Bryodelphax ortholineatus (Bartoš, 1963)
Bryodelphax parvulus Thulin, 1928
Bryodelphax parvuspolaris Kaczmarek, Zawierucha, Smykla & Michalczyk, 2012 <Amended by DeMilio *et al.* 2022a based on type material>
Bryodelphax pucapetricolus DeMilio, Tumanov, Lawton, Kristensen & Hansen, 2022
Bryodelphax sinensis (Pilato, 1974)
Bryodelphax tatrensis (Węglarska, 1959)
Bryodelphax wallacearthuri DeMilio, Tumanov, Lawton, Kristensen & Hansen, 2022
Bryodelphax weglarskae (Pilato, 1972)

Claxtonia Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2019 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d} {16 species}
<Amended by Degma *et al.* 2021>

Claxtonia aliquantilla (Grigarick, Schuster & Nelson, 1983) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Degma *et al.* 2021>
Claxtonia barbarae (Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2002) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>
Claxtonia capillata (Ramazzotti, 1956) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>
Claxtonia corrugicaudata (McInnes, 2010) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>
Claxtonia goni Degma, Meyer & Hinton, 2021
Claxtonia malpighii (Biserov, 1994) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>
Claxtonia marginopora (Grigarick, Schuster & Nelson, 1983) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>
Claxtonia mauccii (Ramazzotti, 1956) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>
Claxtonia molluscorum (Fox & Garcia-Moll, 1962) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>
Claxtonia moniliata (Iharos, 1967) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>
Claxtonia mosaica (Grigarick, Schuster & Nelson, 1983) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Degma *et al.* 2021>
Claxtonia nigripustula (Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Degma *et al.* 2021>
Claxtonia pardalis (Degma & Schill, 2015) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d}
Claxtonia pseudowendti (Dastyk, 1984) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* to *Barbaria* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d; Transferred from *Barbaria* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022a>
Claxtonia vincula (Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>
Claxtonia wendti (Richters, 1903) [*Echiniscus dearmatus* Bartoš, 1935 according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d, *Echiniscus szaboi* Iharos, 1973 as it was already synonymized with *E. dearmatus*] <*E. wendti* and *E. dearmatus* transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d; Redescribed and neotype (from original type locality Svalbard, Norway) designated by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024a>

Cornechiniscus Maucci & Ramazzotti, 1981 {11 species}

<Amended by Gąsiorek 2022>

Cornechiniscus brachycornutus Maucci, 1987 <Amended by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020b based on type material>
Cornechiniscus ceratophorus (Maucci, 1973) <Amended by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020b based on type material>
Cornechiniscus cornutus (Richters, 1907) [*Pseudechiniscus intermedius* Mihelčič, 1970] <Amended by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020b based on Kyrgyz population>
Cornechiniscus holmeni (Petersen, 1951) <Amended by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020b>
Cornechiniscus imperfectus Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2020
Cornechiniscus lobatus (Ramazzotti, 1943) [*Pseudechiniscus cornutus* Mihelčič, 1966] <Amended by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020b>
Cornechiniscus madagascariensis Maucci, 1993 <Amended by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020b>
Cornechiniscus mystacinus Gąsiorek, 2022
Cornechiniscus schrammi (Dastyk, 1979) <Amended by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020b>

Cornechiniscus subcornutus Maucci & Ramazzotti, 1981 <Amended by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020b>

Cornechiniscus tibetanus (Maucci, 1979) <Amended by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020b>

Diploechiniscus Vicente, Fontoura, Cesari, Rebecchi, Guidetti, Serrano & Bertolani, 2013 {5 species}

Diploechiniscus dimorphus Vecchi, Guidetti, Vincenzi, Choong & Calhim, 2024

Diploechiniscus laterosetosus (Ito, 1993) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek 2023>

Diploechiniscus oihonnae (Richters, 1903) [*Echiniscus multispinosus* da Cunha, 1944 according to Vicente *et al.* 2013] <Amended and neotype (from Geiranger, Norway) designated by Kaczmarek *et al.* 2021 (original type locality Merok, Norway; Geiranger is the current name of Merok)>

Diploechiniscus horningi (Schuster & Grigarick, 1971) [Synonymized with *D. oihonnae* by Kaczmarek *et al.* 2021 but reinstated as a valid species by Vecchi *et al.* 2024 based on population from Vancouver Island, Canada (original type localities in Oregon, USA)]

Diploechiniscus polygonalis (Ito, 1993) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek 2023>

Echiniscus C.A.S. Schultze, 1840 {118 119 species + 1 subspecies}
<Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2017b, Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021f and Gąsiorek 2023>

Echiniscus africanus Murray, 1907 <Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b>

Echiniscus angolensis da Cunha & do Nascimento Ribeiro, 1964

Echiniscus aonikenk Gąsiorek, Bochnak, Vončina & Michalczyk, 2021

Echiniscus apuanus M. Bertolani, 1946 {*nomen dubium* according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023}

Echiniscus arcangelii Maucci, 1973-74

Echiniscus arctomys Ehrenberg, 1853 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d}

Echiniscus arthuri Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2005

Echiniscus attenboroughi Gąsiorek, Vončina, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}

Echiniscus azoricus Fontoura, Pilato & Lisi, 2008

Echiniscus baius Marcus, 1928

Echiniscus baloghi Iharos, 1973

Echiniscus becki Schuster & Grigarick, 1966 {Based on type material, additional characters to the original description were added by Gąsiorek 2023}

Echiniscus belloporus Gąsiorek & Kristensen, 2018

Echiniscus bisculptus Maucci, 1983

Echiniscus blumi Richters, 1903 [*Echiniscus ramazzottii* Binda & Pilato, 1969; *Echiniscus bisetosus* Heinis, 1908 according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d; *Echiniscus mediantus* Marcus, 1930 according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d; *Echiniscus blumi schizofilus* Bartoš, 1941 according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023; *Echiniscus trojanus* Maucci, 1973 according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023]

Echiniscus brunus Dey, Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2024

Echiniscus calcaratus Richters, 1908

Echiniscus calvus Marcus, 1931

Echiniscus canadensis Murray, 1910 [*Echiniscus punctulatus* Mihelčič, 1955; *Echiniscus bellus* Mihelčič, 1967]

Echiniscus canedoi da Cunha & do Nascimento Ribeiro, 1962

Echiniscus capensis Gąsiorek, Vončina, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}
Echiniscus cavagnaroi Schuster & Grigarick, 1966 <Amended by Meyer 2016 based on type material>
Echiniscus cervicornis Murray, 1906 {*species inquirenda* according to Marcus 1936}
Echiniscus cheonyoungi Moon & W. Kim, 1994
Echiniscus clevelandi Beasley, 1999
Echiniscus crassispinosus crassispinosus Murray, 1907 <Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b>
Echiniscus crassispinosus fasciatus Marcus, 1928 {*nomen dubium* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}
Echiniscus curiosus Claxton, 1996
Echiniscus darienae Miller, Horning & Dastych, 1995
Echiniscus dentatus Vončina, Gąsiorek, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}
Echiniscus dikenli Maucci, 1973
Echiniscus diploglyptus Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1975
Echiniscus divergens Marcus, 1936
Echiniscus draconis Vončina, Gąsiorek, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}
Echiniscus dreyfusi de Barros, 1942
Echiniscus duboisi Richters, 1902 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}
Echiniscus ehrenbergi Dastych & Kristensen, 1995
Echiniscus elaeinae Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2005
Echiniscus evelinae de Barros, 1942 <Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021f based on Argentinian population (original type locality in São Paulo state, Brasil)>
Echiniscus gemmatus Leong, 2024 {in Leong *et al.* 2024}
Echiniscus gracilis Gąsiorek, Vončina, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}
Echiniscus granulatus (Doyère, 1840) [*Echiniscus crassus* Richters, 1904; *Echiniscus fortis* Bartoš, 1935; *Echiniscus abanti* Maucci, 1973; *Echiniscus egnatiae* Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1979 according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023; *Echiniscus heterospinosus* Maucci, 1954 according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023; *Echiniscus inocelatus* Mihelčič, 1938 according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023 - consequently also *Echiniscus inocellatus* Mihelčič, 1964 which is synonymous with *E. inocelatus* according to Degma & Guidetti 2007] <Redescribed and neotype (from Saint-Maur-des-Fossés, France) designated by Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023 (original type locality Paris, France)>
Echiniscus hoonsooi Moon & W. Kim, 1990
Echiniscus imitans Gąsiorek, Vončina, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}
Echiniscus insuetus Mihelčič, 1967 {*species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d}
Echiniscus insularis Gąsiorek, Vončina & Kiosya, 2021 {in Kiosya *et al.* 2021}
Echiniscus intricatus Gąsiorek, Vončina, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}
Echiniscus irroratus Gąsiorek, Vončina, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}
Echiniscus jamesi Claxton, 1996
Echiniscus kerguelensis Richters, 1904
Echiniscus knowltoni Schuster & Grigarick, 1971
Echiniscus kosickii Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2010
Echiniscus lapponicus Thulin, 1911 <Redescribed by Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023 based on Norwegian population>
Echiniscus latruncularis Gąsiorek, Vončina, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}

***Echiniscus lentiferoides* Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2026**

Echiniscus lentiferus Claxton & Dastych, 2017

Echiniscus lichenorum Maucci, 1983 <Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b based on South African population> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d; Valid species according to Kaczmarek *et al.* 2022a and Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}

Echiniscus lineatus Pilato, Fontoura, Lisi & Beasley, 2008 [*Echiniscus dariae* Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2010 in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019b]

Echiniscus longispinosus Murray, 1907 <Redescribed and neotype (from Western Cape, Tradouw Pass Republic of South Africa) designated by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b>

Echiniscus loxophthalmus Richters, 1911 {*species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d}

Echiniscus manuelae da Cunha & do Nascimento Ribeiro, 1962

Echiniscus marculsi Pilato, Claxton & Binda, 1989

Echiniscus marginatus Binda & Pilato, 1994

Echiniscus marleyi X. Li, 2007 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023}

Echiniscus masculinus Gąsiorek, Vončina & Michalczyk, 2020

Echiniscus meridionalis Murray, 1906 <Transferred to *Testechiniscus* by Kristensen 1987; Re-transferred to *Echiniscus* and redescribed by Gąsiorek 2023 based on South Shetland Islands population>

Echiniscus merokensis Richters, 1904 [*Echiniscus iharosi* Rudescu, 1964; *Echiniscus simba* Marcus, 1928 according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d; *Echiniscus batramiae* Iharos, 1936 according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023; *Echiniscus columinis* Murray, 1911 according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023; *Echiniscus jagodici* Mihelčič, 1951 according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023; *Echiniscus laterospinosus* Rudescu, 1964 according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023; *Echiniscus merokensis suecicus* Thulin, 1911 according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023]

Echiniscus migiurtinus Franceschi, 1957

Echiniscus militaris Murray, 1911 [*Echiniscus hexacanthus* Maucci, 1973 according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023]

Echiniscus minutus Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2024

Echiniscus mongoliensis Iharos, 1973 <*E. filamentosus mongoliensis* elevated to species level by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2017b>

Echiniscus montanus Iharos, 1982

Echiniscus murrayi Iharos, 1969

Echiniscus nelsonae X. Li, L. Wang & Yu, 2007

Echiniscus nepalensis Dastych, 1975

Echiniscus oreas Gąsiorek, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}

Echiniscus ornamentatus Gąsiorek & Kristensen, 2018

Echiniscus pajstunensis Bartoš, 1941 {*nomen dubium* according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023}

Echiniscus pellucidus Gąsiorek, Bochnak, Vončina & Michalczyk, 2021

Echiniscus perarmatus Murray, 1907 [*Echiniscus maesi* Séméria, 1985 according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d] <Redescribed and neotype (from KwaZulu-Natal, Republic of South Africa) designated by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b (original type locality Cape Colony, Republic of South Africa)>

Echiniscus pooensis Rodriguez-Roda, 1948

Echiniscus porabrus Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978

Echiniscus postojnensis Mihelčič, 1967 [*Echiniscus loxophthalmus* Mihelčič, 1939] {*nomen*

dubium according to Dastyč 2015}

Echiniscus punctus McInnes, 1995 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gašiorek & Vončina 2023}

Echiniscus pusae Marcus, 1928

Echiniscus quadrispinosus Richters, 1902 [*Echiniscus scrofa* Richters, 1902; *E. quadrispinosus brachyspinosus* Bartoš, 1934, *E. quadrispinosus cribrosus* Murray, 1907 and *E. quadrispinosus fissispinosus* Murray, 1907 according to Kaczmarek *et al.* 2022a] <Redescribed and neotype (from the original type locality Taunus Mountain Range, Germany) designated by Kaczmarek *et al.* 2022a>

Echiniscus quasiporus Dey, Ostoja-Wilamowski & Michalczyk, 2025

Echiniscus rackae Dastyč, 1986

Echiniscus regularis Gašiorek, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gašiorek *et al.* 2022b}

Echiniscus reymondi Marcus, 1928

Echiniscus robertsi Schuster & Grigarick, 1965

Echiniscus rodnae Claxton, 1996

Echiniscus rugospinosus Marcus, 1928

Echiniscus scabrocirrosus Gašiorek, Vončina, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gašiorek *et al.* 2022b}

Echiniscus scabrospinosus Fontoura, 1982 <Amended by Pilato *et al.* 2008b>

Echiniscus semifoveolatus Ito, 1993 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gašiorek & Michalczyk 2024}

Echiniscus setaceus Gašiorek, Vončina, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gašiorek *et al.* 2022b}

Echiniscus shaanxiensis X. Li, L. Wang & Yu, 2007

Echiniscus siegristi Heinis, 1911

Echiniscus similaris Gašiorek, Vončina, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gašiorek *et al.* 2022b}

Echiniscus siticulosus Gašiorek & Michalczyk, 2020

Echiniscus speciosus Mihelčič, 1967 [*Echiniscus roseus* Mihelčič, 1967] {*species dubia* according to Gašiorek *et al.* 2019d}

Echiniscus spiculifer Schaudinn, 1901 {*species dubia* according to Gašiorek *et al.* 2019d}

Echiniscus spinulosus (Doyère, 1840) [*Echiniscus carusoi* Pilato, 1972 according to Gašiorek & Vončina 2023; *Echiniscus spiniger* Richters, 1904 according to Gašiorek & Sørensen 2024] <Redescribed and neotype (from Andalucia, Spain) designated by Gašiorek & Vončina 2023 (original type locality Saint-Maur-des-Fossés, France)>

Echiniscus succineus Gašiorek & Vončina, 2019

Echiniscus sylvanus Murray, 1910

Echiniscus taibaiensis L. Wang & X. Li, 2005

Echiniscus tamus Mehlen, 1969 <Amended by Miller & Mehlen 2007>

Echiniscus tantulus Gašiorek, Bochnak, Vončina & Kristensen, 2020 {in Bochnak *et al.* 2020}

Echiniscus tenuis Marcus, 1928 {Probably *Bryodelphax* according to Gašiorek *et al.* 2019d}

Echiniscus testudo (Doyère, 1840) [*Echiniscus bellermanni* C.A.S. Schultze, 1840; *Echiniscus inermis* Richters, 1902; *Echiniscus trifilis* Rahm, 1924; *Echiniscus testudo quadrifilis* according to Gašiorek *et al.* 2017b; *Echiniscus filamentosus* Plate, 1888 according to Gašiorek *et al.* 2017b; *Echiniscus glaber* Bartoš, 1937 according to Gašiorek *et al.* 2017b; *Echiniscus peruvianus* Binda & Pilato, 1994 according to Gašiorek *et al.* 2021f] <Redescribed and neotype (from original type locality Paris, France) designated by Gašiorek *et al.* 2017b>

Echiniscus tetraspinosus Gašiorek, Vončina, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gašiorek *et al.*

2022b}

Echiniscus trisetosus Cuénot, 1932 [*Echiniscus storkani* Bartoš, 1940 according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d; *Echiniscus osellai* Maucci, 1975 according to Gąsiorek & Vončina 2023]

Echiniscus tristis Gąsiorek & Kristensen, 2018

Echiniscus tropicalis Binda & Pilato, 1995

Echiniscus tympanista Murray, 1911

Echiniscus velaminis Murray, 1910

Echiniscus virginicus Riggin, 1962 <Amended by Christenberry & Mason 1979>

Echiniscus weisseri Maucci, 1978

Echiniscus zetotrymus Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978

Hypechiniscus Thulin, 1928 {10 species}

Hypechiniscus africanus Gąsiorek, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}

Hypechiniscus cataractus Gąsiorek, Oczkowski, Kristensen & Michalczyk, 2021 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021d}

Hypechiniscus crassus Gąsiorek, Vončina, Kristensen & Michalczyk, 2021

Hypechiniscus daedalus Gąsiorek, Oczkowski, Bartels, Nelson, Kristensen & Michalczyk, 2021 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021d}

Hypechiniscus exarmatus (Murray, 1907) [*Oreella breviclava* Grigarick, Schuster & Nelson, 1983]

Hypechiniscus fengi X.-Z. Sun & X. Li, 2013 <Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021d>

Hypechiniscus flavus Gąsiorek, Oczkowski, Suzuki, Kristensen & Michalczyk, 2021 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021d}

Hypechiniscus geminus Gąsiorek, Oczkowski, Suzuki, Kristensen & Michalczyk, 2021 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021d}

Hypechiniscus gladiator (Murray, 1905) [*Parechiniscus unispinosus* da Cunha, 1947] <Amended, the subspecies *bigladii* and the form *fissigladii* suppressed, the form *spinulosa* considered invalid (all three previously described by Iharos 1973) by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021d>

Hypechiniscus papillifer (Robotti, 1972) {Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021d}

Kristenseniscus Gąsiorek, Morek, Stec & Michalczyk, 2019 {5 species}

Kristenseniscus exanthema Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2024

Kristenseniscus kofordi (Schuster & Grigarick, 1966) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Kristenseniscus limai (da Cunha & do Nascimento Ribeiro, 1964) {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d} <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Kristenseniscus tessellatus (Murray, 1910) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Kristenseniscus walteri (Pilato & Lisi, 2003) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Mopsechiniscus du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1944 {6 species}

Mopsechiniscus franciscae Guidetti, Rebecchi, Cesari & McInnes, 2014

Mopsechiniscus frenoti Dastych, 1999

Mopsechiniscus granulosus Mihelčič, 1967
Mopsechiniscus imberbis (Richters, 1908)
Mopsechiniscus schusteri Dastych, 1999
Mopsechiniscus tasmanicus Dastych & Moscal, 1992

Multipseudechiniscus Schulte & Miller, 2011 {1 species}
<Amended by Miller *et al.* 2012>

Multipseudechiniscus raneyi (Grigarick, Mihelčič & Schuster, 1964) <Transferred from
Pseudechiniscus by Schulte & Miller, 2011>

Nebularmis Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2019 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d} {13 species}
<Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021b>

Nebularmis auratus Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2021 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021b}
Nebularmis bhutanensis Veloso, Fontoura & Gąsiorek, 2021 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021b}
Nebularmis burmensis Gąsiorek & Vončina, 2021 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021b}
Nebularmis carsicus (Mihelčič, 1966) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>
{*species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d}
Nebularmis cirinoi (Binda & Pilato, 1993) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.*
2019d>
Nebularmis crebraclava (X.-Z. Sun, X. Li & Feng, 2014) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* to
Claxtonia by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d; Transferred from *Claxtonia* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021b>
Nebularmis indicus Gąsiorek, Ciosek & Michalczyk, 2021 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021b}
Nebularmis japonicus (Morikawa, 1951) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.*
2019d> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019a, c}
Nebularmis markezi (Mihelčič, 1971/72) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.*
2019d> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019a}
Nebularmis nobilis (Mihelčič, 1967) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>
{*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015; *species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.*
2019d}
Nebularmis phocae (du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1944) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek
et al. 2019d> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019a, d}
Nebularmis reticulatus (Murray, 1905) [*Nebularmis mihelcici* (Iharos, 1973) according to
Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019a] <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d; Redescribed
and neotype (from original type locality Loch Ness shore, Scotland, UK) designated by
Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019a; *Nebularmis mihelcici* transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.*
2019d> {*Nebularmis mihelcici* - *species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d}
Nebularmis tardus (Mihelčič, 1951) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>
{*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015; *species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.*
2019d}

Novechiniscus Kristensen, 1987 {1 species}

Novechiniscus armadilloides (R.O. Schuster, 1975)

Parechiniscus Cuénot, 1926 {1 species}
<Amended by DeMilio *et al.* 2022b>

Parechiniscus chitonides Cuénot, 1926

Polyacanthechiniscus Kihm & Gąsiorek, 2026 {in Kihm *et al.* 2026} {2 species}
Polyacanthechiniscus goedeni (Grigarick, Mihelčič & Schuster, 1964) <Transferred from *Pseudechiniscus* to *Acanthechiniscus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a; transferred from *Acanthechiniscus* by Kihm *et al.* 2026>
Polyacanthechiniscus islandicus (Richters, 1904) <Transferred from *Pseudechiniscus* to *Acanthechiniscus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a; transferred from *Acanthechiniscus* by Kihm *et al.* 2026>

Proechiniscus Kristensen, 1987 {1 species}
Proechiniscus hanneae (Petersen, 1951)

Pseudechiniscus Thulin, 1911 {2 subgenera}
<Amended by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Subgenus: *Pseudechiniscus* Thulin, 1911 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021c} {29 30 species + 1 subspecies}

Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) alberti Dastych, 1987
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) aquatilis Vončina, Gąsiorek, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) asper Abe, Utsugi & Takeda, 1998 <Amended by Vončina *et al.* 2020>
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) beasleyi X. Li, L. Wang & Yu, 2007
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) bidenticulatus Bartoš, 1963
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) brevimontanus Kendall-Fite & Nelson, 1996
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) chengi Xue, X. Li, L. Wang, Xian, H. Chen, 2017
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) clavatus Mihelčič, 1955 {*species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021c}
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) dicrani Mihelčič, 1938 {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015}
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) ehrenbergi Roszkowska, Grobys, T. Bartylak & Kaczmarek, 2020 {in Roszkowska *et al.* 2020}
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) facettalis Petersen, 1951 [*Pseudechiniscus pseudoconifer facettalis* Maucci, 1954]
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) formosus Gąsiorek, Vončina, Kristensen & Michalczyk, 2021
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) goldyni Warguła, Kayastha, Polishchuk, Nawrot, Krakowiak, T. Bartylak, Gawlak & Kaczmarek, 2025
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) insolitus Maucci, 1991
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) jubatus Biserov, 1990
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) lacyformis Roszkowska, Grobys, T. Bartylak & Kaczmarek, 2020 {in Roszkowska *et al.* 2020}
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) lalitae Kayastha, T. Bartylak, Gawlak & Kaczmarek, 2020
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) linnaei Vončina, Gąsiorek, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) marinae Bartoš, 1934 {Synonymized to *Pseudechiniscus novaezeelandiae*, accepting it as *P. novaezeelandiae* forma *marinae* by Marcus 1936} <re-

elevated to species level by Tumanov 2020a>
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) megacephalus Mihelčič, 1951 {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015 and Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021c}
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) nataliae Biserov & Maucci, 1986 {in Biserov 1986}
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) occultus Dastych, 1980
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) papillosus X. Li, L. Wang, Y. Liu & Su, 2005
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) pseudoconifer Ramazzotti, 1943
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) ramazzottii ramazzottii Maucci, 1952
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) ramazzottii facettalis Iharos, 1964 [*Pseudechiniscus ramazzottii lineatus* Maucci, 1973-74]
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) scortecii Franceschi, 1952
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus)shintai Vončina, Kristensen & Gąsiorek, 2020
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) suillus (Ehrenberg, 1853) [*Echiniscus mutabilis* Murray, 1905] <Redescribed and neotype (from the original type locality Monte Rosa mountain massif, Aosta Valley, Italy) designated by Grobys *et al.* 2020>
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) totoro Gąsiorek, Vončina, Kristensen & Michalczyk, 2021
Pseudechiniscus (Pseudechiniscus) xiai L. Wang, Xue & X. Li, 2018

Subgenus: *Meridioniscus* Gąsiorek, Vončina & Michalczyk, 2023 {17 19 species + 3 forms}
 {First proposed by Gąsiorek *et al.* (2021c) without the ZooBank registration number required for works issued and distributed electronically, consequently the name *Meridioniscus* was not made officially available until its new establishment by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2023}
Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) angelusalas Roszkowska, Grobys, T. Bartylak & Kaczmarek, 2020 {in Roszkowska *et al.* 2020}
Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) bartkei Węglarska, 1962
Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) celebesiensis Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2024
Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) conifer (Richters, 1904)
Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) dastychi Roszkowska, Grobys, T. Bartylak & Kaczmarek, 2020 {in Roszkowska *et al.* 2020}
Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) dreyeri Gąsiorek, Vončina, Kristensen & Michalczyk, 2021
***Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) goldsteini* Kayastha, M. Bartylak, T. Bartylak, Gawlak, Sługocki & Kaczmarek, 2026**
Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) indistinctus Roszkowska, Grobys, T. Bartylak & Kaczmarek, 2020 {in Roszkowska *et al.* 2020}
Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) juanita de Barros, 1939 [*Pseudechiniscus suillus franciscae* de Barros, 1942]
Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) mascarenensis Kiosya, Vončina & Gąsiorek, 2021
Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) novaezeelandiae novaezeelandiae (Richters, 1908)
Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) novaezeelandiae forma *aspinosa* Iharos, 1963 {*nomen dubium* according to Tumanov 2020a}
Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) novaezeelandiae forma *dorsospinosa* Iharos, 1963 {*nomen dubium* according to Tumanov 2020a}
Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) novaezeelandiae forma *laterospinosa* Iharos, 1963 {*nomen dubium* according to Tumanov 2020a}
Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) quadrilobatus Iharos, 1969 [*Pseudechiniscus gullii* Pilato & Lisi, 2006 according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021c, *Pseudechiniscus pilatoi* X. Li, 2007

according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021c]

Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) rosinae Fassina, Mioduchowska, Wargula & Kaczmarek, 2025
{in Fassina *et al.* 2025}

Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) saltensis Rocha, Doma, Gonzales Reyes & Lisi, 2020

Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) santomensis Fontoura, Pilato & Lisi, 2010

Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) spinirectus Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2001

Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) titianae Vecchi, Cesari, Bertolani, Jönsson, Rebecchi & Guidetti, 2016a

Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) yunnanensis L. Wang, 2009

Pseudechiniscus (Meridioniscus) wallacei Vončina, Gąsiorek, Morek & Michalczyk, 2022 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2022b}

not included in any subgenus {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021c} {4 species}

Pseudechiniscus bispinosus (Murray, 1907) {Probably belongs in a different genus according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021c}

Pseudechiniscus jiroveci Bartoš, 1963 {*nomen dubium* according to Tumanov 2020a}

Pseudechiniscus shilinensis T. Yang, 2002 {*nomen dubium* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021c}

Pseudechiniscus transsylvanicus Iharos, 1936 {Probably belongs in a different genus according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021c}

Stellariscus Gąsiorek, Suzuki, Kristensen & Michalczyk, 2018 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2018c} {3 species}

Stellariscus elegans (Richters, 1907) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2018c>

Stellariscus latifasciatus (Dudichev & Biserov, 2000) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2018c>

Stellariscus pseudelegans (Séméria, 1994) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2018c>

Testechiniscus Kristensen, 1987 {3 4 species + 1 subspecies}

<Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2018b, and Gąsiorek 2023 and Tsvetkova & Tumanov 2026>

Testechiniscus impenetrabilis Tsvetkova & Tumanov, 2026

Testechiniscus laterculus (Schuster, Grigarick & Toftner, 1980) <Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2018b>

Testechiniscus macronyx (Richters, 1908) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by McInnes 1994>

Testechiniscus spitsbergensis spitsbergensis (Scourfield, 1897) [*Echiniscus clavisetosus* Mihelčič, 1958; *Echiniscus marinellae* Bartoš, 1935; *Echiniscus melanophthalmus* Bartoš, 1936; *Echiniscus menzeli* Heinis, 1917; *Echiniscus rosaliae* Mihelčič, 1951; *Echiniscus spinuloides* Murray, 1907] <Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2018b>

Testechiniscus spitsbergensis tropicalis Gąsiorek, Stec, Zawierucha, Kristensen & Michalczyk, 2018

Viridiscus Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2019 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d} {6 species}

Viridiscus celatus Momeni, Gąsiorek, Nelson & Michalczyk, 2023 {in Momeni *et al.* 2023}

Viridiscus clavispinosus (Fontoura, Pilato & Lisi, 2011) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Momeni *et al.* 2023}

Viridiscus perviridis (Ramazzotti, 1959) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Viridiscus viridianus (Pilato, Fontoura & Lisi, 2007) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d; Redescribed by Momeni *et al.* 2023 based on populations from Alabama and Florida, USA>

Viridiscus viridis (Murray, 1910) <Amended by Pilato *et al.* 2008a; Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Viridiscus viridissimus (Péterfi, 1956) [*Viridiscus miraviridis* Nelson, Adkins Fletcher, Guidetti, Roszkowska, Grobys & Kaczmarek, ~~2021~~ 2020 according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2021e] <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019d>

Zealandiscus Kaczmarek & Roszkowska, 2021 {1 species}

Zealandiscus palmai (Dastych, 1997) <Transferred from *Echiniscus* by Kaczmarek & Roszkowska 2021>

Class: MESOTARDIGRADA Rahm, 1937 {*nomen dubium* according to Grothman *et al.* 2017}
{1 order}

Order: THERMOZODIA Ramazzotti & Maucci, 1983 {1 family}

Family: Thermozodiidae Rahm, 1937 {1 genus}

Thermozodium Rahm, 1937 {1 species}

Thermozodium esakii Rahm, 1937

Class: EUTARDIGRADA Richters, 1926 {2 orders}

{Guil *et al.* 2019 proposed new class APOTARDIGRADA Guil, Jørgensen & Kristensen, 2019 for the order APOCHELA, suppressed order PARACHELA and replaced it with class EUTARDIGRADA and elevated superfamilies Eohypsibioidea, Hypsibioidea, Isohypsibioidea and Macrobiotoidea to orders. Morek *et al.* 2020b suppressed all these taxonomic acts}

Order: APOCHELA Schuster, Nelson, Grigarick & Christenberry, 1980 {1 family}
<Amended by Morek *et al.* 2020b>

Family: Milnesiidae Ramazzotti, 1962 {4 genera}
<Amended by Morek *et al.* 2020b>

Bergtrollus Dastych, 2011 {1 species}

Bergtrollus dzimbowski Dastych, 2011

Limmenius Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978 {1 species}

Limmenius porcellus Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978

Milnesioides Claxton, 1999 {1 species}

Milnesioides exsertum Claxton, 1999

Milnesium Doyère, 1840 {~~53~~ 58 species + 1 subspecies}
<Amended by Morek *et al.* 2020b>

Milnesium alabamae Wallendorf & Miller, 2009
Milnesium almatyense Tumanov, 2006 <Amended by Morek *et al.* 2020a>
Milnesium alpigenum Ehrenberg, 1853 <Redescribed and neotype (from the original type locality Monte Rosa mountain massif, Aosta Valley, Italy) designated by Morek *et al.* 2019b>
 {Valid according to Morek *et al.* 2016}
Milnesium antarcticum Tumanov, 2006
Milnesium argentinum Roszkowska, Ostrowska & Kaczmarek, 2015
Milnesium asiaticum Tumanov, 2006
Milnesium barbadosense Meyer & Hinton, 2012
Milnesium beasleyi Kaczmarek, Jakubowska & Michalczyk, 2012
Milnesium beatae Roszkowska, Ostrowska & Kaczmarek, 2015
Milnesium berladicorum Ciobanu, Zawierucha, Moglan & Kaczmarek, 2014
Milnesium bohleberi Bartels, Nelson, Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2014
Milnesium brachyungue Binda & Pilato, 1990
Milnesium burgessi Schlabach, Donaldson, Hobelman, Miller & Lowman, 2018
Milnesium cassandrae Moreno-Talamantes, Roszkowska, García-Aranda, Flores-Maldonado & Kaczmarek, 2019
Milnesium decorum Morek, Wałach & Michalczyk, 2022
Milnesium dornensis Ciobanu, Roszkowska & Kaczmarek, 2015
Milnesium dujiangensis T. Yang, 2003 {*nomen dubium* according to Morek *et al.* 2016}
Milnesium eury stomum Maucci, 1991 <Amended by Michalczyk *et al.* 2012 based on holotype>
Milnesium fridae Moreno-Talamantes, León-Espinosa, García-Aranda, Flores-Maldonado & Kaczmarek, 2020
Milnesium grandicupula Kihm, Zawierucha, Rho & Park, 2025
Milnesium granulatum Ramazzotti, 1962 <*M. tardigradum granulatum* amended based on paratype and elevated to species level by Michalczyk *et al.* 2012>
Milnesium guanyinensis Yuan, Q. Liu, Y. Wang, L. Liu, Y. Chen & X. Li, 2023
Milnesium inceptum Morek, Suzuki, Schill, Georgiev, Yankova, Marley & Michalczyk, 2019
Milnesium iniquum Brotto-Guidetti, Morek & Garraffoni, 2024
Milnesium irenae Rocha, González-Reyes, Ostertag & Lisi, 2022
Milnesium jacobii Meyer & Hinton, 2010
Milnesium katarzynae Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Beasley, 2004
Milnesium kogui Londoño, Daza, Caicedo, Quiroga & Kaczmarek, 2015
Milnesium krzysztofi Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2007
Milnesium lagniappe Meyer, Hinton & Dupré, 2013
Milnesium longiungue Tumanov, 2006
Milnesium matheusi Kaczmarek, Grobys, Kulpa, T. Bartylak, Kmita, M. Kepel, A. Kepel & Roszkowska, 2019
Milnesium milenae Kayastha, Warguła, T. Bartylak, Mioduchowska, Gawlak & Kaczmarek, 2025
Milnesium minutum Pilato & Lisi, 2016
Milnesium myriae Kayastha, Warguła, T. Bartylak, Mioduchowska, Gawlak & Kaczmarek, 2025
Milnesium pacificum Sugiura, Minato, Matsumoto & Suzuki, 2020
Milnesium pelufforum Rocha, González-Reyes, Ostertag & Lisi, 2022
Milnesium pentapapillatum Ciosek, Morek & Michalczyk, 2020 {in Morek *et al.* 2020b}
Milnesium pseudotardigradum Surmacz, Morek & Michalczyk, 2019
Milnesium quadrifidum Nederström, 1919 {Valid according to Morek *et al.* 2016}

Milnesium quiranae Rocha, González-Reyes, Ostertag & Lisi, 2022
Milnesium rastrum Suzuki, Sugiura, Tsujimoto & McInnes, 2023 {in Suzuki *et al.* 2023}
Milnesium reductum Tumanov, 2006 <Amended by Morek *et al.* 2020a>
Milnesium reticulatum Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2002 <Amended by Morek *et al.* 2022>
Milnesium sandrae Pilato & Lisi, 2016
Milnesium shilohae Meyer, 2015
Milnesium swansoni Young, Chappell, Miller & Lowman, 2016
Milnesium swolenskyi Bertolani & Grimaldi, 2000 {fossil species}
Milnesium tardigradum tardigradum Doyère, 1840 <Redescribed and neotype (from Zeesen, Wildau, Germany) designated by Michalczyk *et al.* 2012 (original type locality Saint-Maur-des-Fossés, France); Amended by Morek *et al.* 2019a>
Milnesium tardigradum trispinosa Rahm, 1931 {*nomen dubium* according to Morek *et al.* 2016; Not valid according to Suzuki 2016}
Milnesium tetralamellatum Pilato & Binda, 1991
Milnesium tumanovi Pilato, Sabella & Lisi, 2016
***Milnesium utsugii* Sugiura & Suzuki, 2025**
Milnesium validum Pilato, Sabella, D'Urso & Lisi, 2017
Milnesium variefidum Morek, Gąsiorek, Stec, Blagden & Michalczyk, 2016
Milnesium vorax Pilato, Sabella & Lisi, 2016
***Milnesium warrenwilsonensis* Bartels, Kayastha, T. Bartylak, Mioduchowska, Dmuchowska & Kaczmarek, 2025**
Milnesium wrightae Kaczmarek, Grobys, Kulpa, T. Bartylak, Kmita, M. Kepel, A. Kepel & Roszkowska, 2019
Milnesium zsalakoe Meyer & Hinton, 2010

Order: PARACHELA Schuster, Nelson, Grigarick & Christenberry, 1980 {4 superfamilies}

Superfamily: Eohypsibioidea Bertolani & Kristensen, 1987 {in Marley *et al.* 2011} {1 family}

Family: Eohypsibiidae Bertolani & Kristensen, 1987 {3 genera}
 [Amphibolidae Bertolani, 1981]
 <Amended by Trygvadóttir & Kristensen 2011>

Austeruseus Trygvadóttir & Kristensen, 2011 {3 species}
Austeruseus balduri Trygvadóttir & Kristensen 2011
Austeruseus faeroensis Trygvadóttir & Kristensen 2011
Austeruseus rokuri Trygvadóttir & Kristensen 2011

Bertolanus Özdikmen, 2008 {8 species}
 [Amphibolus Bertolani, 1981 according to Özdikmen 2008]
 <Amended by Trygvadóttir & Kristensen 2011>
Bertolanus birnae Hansen, Kristensen, Bertolani & Guidetti, 2016
Bertolanus mahunkai (Iharos, 1971)
Bertolanus markevichi (Biserov, 1992)
Bertolanus nebulosus (Dastych, 1983)
Bertolanus portucalensis Fontoura, Pilato, Lisi & Morais, 2009

Bertolanus smreczynskii (Węglarska, 1970)
Bertolanus volubilis (Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1975)
Bertolanus weglarskae (Dastych, 1972)

Eohypsibius Kristensen, 1982 {2 species}
<Amended by Trygvadóttir & Kristensen 2011>

Eohypsibius najdae Kristensen, 1982
Eohypsibius terrestris Ito, 1988

Superfamily: Hypsibioidea Pilato, 1969 {in Marley *et al.* 2011} {7 families}
<Amended by Bertolani *et al.* 2014 and by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2018a>

Family: Acutuncidae Vecchi, Tsvetkova, Stec, Ferrari, Calhim & Tumanov, 2023 {1 genus}

Acutuncus Pilato & Binda, 1997 {4 species}
<Transferred from Hypsibiinae to *incerta subfamilia* within Hypsibiidae by Bertolani *et al.* 2014;
Transferred from Hypsibiidae and amended by Vecchi *et al.* 2023b>
Acutuncus antarcticus (Richters, 1904) [*Hypsibius simoizumii* Sudzuki, 1964]
Acutuncus giovanninae Vecchi, Tsvetkova, Stec, Ferrari, Calhim & Tumanov, 2023
Acutuncus mariae Zawierucha, 2020 {in Zawierucha *et al.* 2020}
Acutuncus mecuffi Vecchi, Tsvetkova, Stec, Ferrari, Calhim & Tumanov, 2023

Family: Calohypsibiidae Pilato, 1969 {1 genus}
<Amended by Bertolani *et al.* 2014 and by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019c>

Calohypsibius Thulin, 1928 {3 species}
Calohypsibius maliki Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2005
Calohypsibius ornatus (Richters, 1900) [*Hypsibius (Calohypsibius) armatus* Bartoš, 1938;
Hypsibius (Calohypsibius) intermedius Mihelčič, 1939]
Calohypsibius schusteri Nelson & McGlothlin, 1996

Family: Hypsibiidae Pilato, 1969 {2 subfamilies}
<Amended by Bertolani *et al.* 2014 and by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2018a>

Subfamily: Diphasconinae Dastych, 1992 {3 genera}
<Amended by Bertolani *et al.* 2014 and by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020a>

Diphascon Plate, 1888 {41 species + 1 subspecies}
<Amended by Bertolani *et al.* 2014>
Diphascon alpinum Murray, 1906 {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015 and Tumanov & Tsvetkova 2023}
Diphascon australianum Pilato & Binda, 1998
Diphascon bicorne (Mihelčič, 1971) {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015}
Diphascon bidropion Ito, 1995
Diphascon birklehofti Rolf Schuster, 1999
Diphascon chilense Plate, 1888 {*species inquirenda* according to Dastych 2002/2003, *nomen*

dubium according to Dastych 2015}
Diphascon claxtonae Pilato & Binda, 1998
Diphascon coniferens (Bartoš, 1960)
Diphascon dastychi Pilato & Binda, 1999
Diphascon dolomiticum Pilato & Bertolani, 2005
Diphascon faialense Fontoura & Pilato, 2007
Diphascon greveni Dastych, 1984 <Transferred to *Adropion* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Re-transferred to *Diphascon* by Tumanov & Tsvetkova 2023; Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>
Diphascon halapiense (Iharos, 1964) <Transferred to *Pilatobius* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Re-transferred to *Diphascon* by Tumanov 2018>
Diphascon higginsii Binda, 1971
Diphascon ~~humieus~~ humicum Bertolani, Guidetti & Rebecchi, 1994 {We propose changing the ending of the species name because the genus *Diphascon* has a neuter gender.}
Diphascon hydrophilum Pilato, Binda, Bertolani & Lisi, 2005
Diphascon iharosi Vargha, 1995
Diphascon langhovdense (Sudzuki, 1964)
Diphascon marcuzzii (Mihelčič, 1971)
Diphascon mariae (Mihelčič, 1951) {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015}
Diphascon mauccii Dastych & McInnes, 1996 <Transferred to *Adropion* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Re-transferred to *Diphascon* by Tumanov & Tsvetkova 2023>
Diphascon ~~mirabilis~~ mirabile Dastych, 1984 {We propose changing the ending of the species name because the genus *Diphascon* has a neuter gender.}
Diphascon mitrense Pilato, Binda & Qualtieri, 1999
Diphascon nelsonae Pilato, Binda, Bertolani & Lisi, 2005
Diphascon nobilei (Binda, 1969)
Diphascon ongulense (Morikawa, 1962)
Diphascon pingue pingue (Marcus, 1936)
Diphascon pingue brunsvicense Argue, 1972
Diphascon pinguiforme Pilato & Binda, 1997/98
Diphascon platyungue Pilato, Binda, Bertolani & Lisi, 2005
Diphascon polare Pilato & Binda, 1999
Diphascon puchalskii Kaczmarek, Parnikoza, Gawlak, Esefeld, Peter, Kozeretska & Roszkowska, 2018
Diphascon punctatum (Iharos, 1962)
Diphascon puniceum (Jennings, 1976)
Diphascon rivulare (Mihelčič, 1967) {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015}
Diphascon rudnickii Kaczmarek, Parnikoza, Gawlak, Esefeld, Peter, Kozeretska & Roszkowska, 2018
Diphascon sanae Dastych, Ryan & Watkins, 1990
Diphascon serratum Pilato, Binda, Bertolani & Lisi, 2005
Diphascon speciosum (Mihelčič, 1971) {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015}
Diphascon stappersi Richters, 1911
Diphascon victoriae Pilato & Binda, 1999
Diphascon zaniawi Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2004

Kararehius Zawierucha, Stec & Shain, 2023 {in Zawierucha *et al.* 2023} {4 species}
Kararehius behanae (Dastych, 1987) <Transferred from *Adropion* by Zawierucha *et al.* 2023>
Kararehius gregorii Zawierucha, 2023 {in Zawierucha *et al.* 2023}
Kararehius tricuspidatum (Binda & Pilato, 2000) <Transferred from *Adropion* by Zawierucha *et al.* 2023>
Kararehius triodon (Maucci, 1996) <Transferred from *Adropion* by Zawierucha *et al.* 2023>

Kopakaius Zawierucha & Shain, 2023 {in Zawierucha *et al.* 2023} {1 species}
Kopakaius nicolae Zawierucha, 2023 {in Zawierucha *et al.* 2023}

Subfamily: Hypsibiinae Pilato, 1969 {4 genera}
<Amended by Bertolani *et al.* 2014>

Borealibius Pilato, Guidetti, Rebecchi, Lisi, Hansen & Bertolani, 2006 {1 species}
Borealibius zetlandicus (Murray, 1907)

Cryobiotus Dastych, 2019 {4 species}
Cryobiotus janetscheki (Ramazzotti, 1968) <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Dastych 2019>
Cryobiotus klebelsbergi (Mihelčič, 1959) <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Dastych 2019>
Cryobiotus thaleri (Dastych, 2004) <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Dastych 2019>
Cryobiotus roswithae Dastych, 2019

Hypsibius Ehrenberg, 1848 {~~34~~ 32 species}
<Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2018a>
Hypsibius allisoni Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978
Hypsibius antonovae (Biserov, 1990)
Hypsibius choucoutiensis Rahm, 1937
Hypsibius convergens (Urbanowicz, 1925)
Hypsibius conwentzii Kaczmarek, Parnikoza, Gawlak, Esefeld, Peter, Kozeretska & Roszkowska, 2018
Hypsibius dujardini (Doyère, 1840) [*Macrobiotus palustris* Dujardin, 1851; *Macrobiotus lacustris* Dujardin, 1851; *Macrobiotus tetradactylus* Lance, 1896; *Macrobiotus samoanus* Richters, 1908; *Macrobiotus breckneri* Richters, 1910; *Macrobiotus ursellus* Della Valle, 1915; *Hypsibius murrayi* Marcus, 1929] <Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2018a>
Hypsibius exemplaris Gąsiorek, Stec, Morek & Michalczyk, 2018
Hypsibius fuhrmanni (Heinis, 1914) {Subjectively invalid according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2018a}
Hypsibius giusepperamazzotti Sudzuki, 1975
Hypsibius henanensis Wang, Li, M. Yang & L. Zhang, 2024
Hypsibius hypostomus Bartoš, 1935
Hypsibius iskandarovi Tumanov, 1997
Hypsibius kunmingensis T. Yang, 2002
Hypsibius maculatus Iharos, 1969
Hypsibius marcelli Pilato, 1990
Hypsibius microps Thulin, 1928 <Amended by Kaczmarek & Michalczyk 2009>
Hypsibius montanus Iharos, 1940 [*Hypsibius iharosi* Bartoš, 1941 according to Degma & Guidetti 2007]

Hypsibius morikawai Ito, 1995
Hypsibius multituberculatus Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2003
Hypsibius murrayi (Richters, 1907) [*Hypsibius heardensis* Miller, McInnes & Bergstrom, 2005 according to Dastych 2018] <Redescribed by Dastych 2018 based on type specimens and additional material from South Georgia and Kerguelen>
Hypsibius nivalis Ono, Takeuchi & Zawierucha, 2022
Hypsibius novaezeelandiae Pilato & Binda, 1997
Hypsibius pachyunguis Maucci, 1996
Hypsibius pallidus Thulin, 1911 <Amended by Kaczmarek & Michalczyk 2009>
Hypsibius pedrotii Bertolani, Manicardi & Gibertoni, 1987
Hypsibius pradellii Bertolani & Rebecchi, 1996
Hypsibius repentinus Tumanov & Avdeeva, 2021
Hypsibius septulatus Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2004
Hypsibius seychellensis Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2006
Hypsibius shaanxiensis H. Li & X. Li, 2008
Hypsibius valentinae Pilato, Kiosya, Lisi & Sabella, 2012
Hypsibius vaskelae Tumanov, 2018

Parahypsibius Gąsiorek, 2024 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024c} {9 species}
Parahypsibius biscuitiformis (Bartoš, 1960) <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024c>
Parahypsibius calcaratus (Bartoš, 1935) <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024c>
Parahypsibius camelopardalis (Ramazzotti & Maucci, 1983) <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024c>
Parahypsibius macrocalcaratus (Beasley, 1988) <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024c>
Parahypsibius ragonesei (Binda & Pilato, 1985) <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024c>
Parahypsibius roanensis (Nelson & McGlothlin, 1993) <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024c>
Parahypsibius scabropygus (Cuénot, 1929) <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024c>
Parahypsibius runae (Bartoš, 1941) <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024c>
Parahypsibius stiliferus (Abe, 2004) <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024c>

Incerta subfamilia {according to Bertolani *et al.* 2014}

Mixibius Pilato, 1992 {11 species}
{To be confirmed in the family Isohypsibiidae, see Marley *et al.* 2011}
<Transferred from Isohypsibiidae by Bertolani *et al.* 2014>
Mixibius felix Pilato, Sabella, D'Urso & Lisi, 2017
Mixibius fueginus Pilato & Binda, 1996
Mixibius gibbosus Lisi, Daza, Londoño & Quiroga, 2022
Mixibius ninguidus Biserov, 1999
Mixibius ornatus Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2002
Mixibius parvus Lisi, Sabella & Pilato, 2014

Mixibius pilatoi L. Wang, 2009
Mixibius saracenus (Pilato, 1973)
Mixibius schnurrae Pilato, Lisi & Binda, 2010
Mixibius sutirae Pilato, Binda & Lisi 2004
Mixibius tibetanus H. Li & X. Li, 2008

Incerta subfamilia {according to Mapalo *et al.* 2024}

Beorn Cooper, 1964 {1 species}

<Transferred from the family Beornidae Cooper, 1964 (with unclear placement into any superfamily according to Marley *et al.* 2011) by Mapalo *et al.* 2024>

Beorn leggi Cooper, 1964 {fossil species}

Family: Itaquasconidae Rudescu, 1964 {12 genera}

<Amended by Bertolani *et al.* 2014 and by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020a; Elevated from the subfamily level in Hypsibiidae by Tumanov & Tsvetkova 2023 however, Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b do not recognized the validity of this proposal>

{Rudescu (1964) first published the name of the family Itaquasconidae based on draft of the monograph by Bartoš (1967) which he lent to Rudescu and which was finally published later than it was planned}

Adropion Pilato, 1987 {12 species}

<Subgenus *Adropion* of the genus *Diphascon* elevated to genus level and transferred from Diphasconinae by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Amended by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020a>

Adropion afroglacialis Zawierucha, Gąsiorek & Buda, 2018 {in Zawierucha *et al.* 2018a}

Adropion belgicae (Richters, 1911) <Amended by Bernard 1977 and by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>

Adropion camtchaticum Tumanov & Kalimullin, 2024

Adropion diphasconiellum (Ito, 1991) <*Fujiscon diphasconiellum* Ito, 1991 was synonymized with *Adropion belgicae* by Maucci 1996; Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b considered it as a valid species>

Adropion fagineum Vecchi, 2024

Adropion gani (X.-Z. Sun, X. Li & Feng, 2014) {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b}

Adropion gordonense (Pilato, Claxton & Horning, 1991)

Adropion linzhiensis (X. Li, 2007)

Adropion marcusii (Rudescu, 1964) <Transferred from *Mesocrista* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2016> {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015; *species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2016; For taxonomic status of the species see Gąsiorek *et al.* 2016}

Adropion ommatophorum (Thulin, 1911) <*Adropion scoticum ommatophorum* elevated to species level by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>

Adropion onorei (Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2002)

Adropion scoticum (Murray, 1905) [*Diphascon crozetense* Richters, 1907] <Redescribed and neotype (from Drum Castle, Drumoak Scotland) designated by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b (original type locality areas around Edinburgh, Scotland); *Adropion scoticum qinlingensis* (X. Li & Y. Liu, 2005) suppressed by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>

Arctodiphascon Tumanov & Tsvetkova, 2023 {2 species}

Arctodiphascon tenue (Thulin, 1928) <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Tumanov & Tsvetkova 2023> {Based on type material, additional character to the original description was added by Tumanov & Tsvetkova 2023}

Arctodiphascon wuyingensis (X.-L. Sun, J.-Y. Zhang, N. Wang, M. Zhao & Luo, 2020)
<Tentatively transferred from *Diphascon* by Tumanov & Tsvetkova 2023>

Astatumen Pilato, 1997 {4 species}

<Amended by Tumanov & Tsvetkova 2023>

Astatumen bartosi (Węglarska, 1959)

Astatumen tamaensis (Sudzuki, 1975)

Astatumen tamurai (Ito, 1990)

Astatumen trinacriae (Arcidiacono, 1962) [*Itaquascon ramazzottii* Iharos, 1966]

Bindius Pilato, 2009 {1 species}

<Transferred from *Diphasconinae* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014>

Bindius triquetrus Pilato, 2009

Guidettion Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2020 {6 species}

{The genus described in Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2020a, Supporting Information}

Guidettion arduifrons (Thulin, 1928) <Transferred from *Adropion* by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020a> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b}

Guidettion clavatum (Bartoš, 1935) <Transferred from *Adropion* by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020a>

Guidettion modestum (Binda, Pilato & Dastych, 1984) <Transferred from *Adropion* by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020a>

Guidettion montigenum (Pilato & Dastych, 1974) <Transferred from *Adropion* by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020a>

Guidettion prorsirostre (Thulin, 1928) [*Guidettion carolae* (Binda & Pilato, 1969), previously transferred from *Adropion* by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020a, synonym according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b] <Transferred from *Adropion* by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020a; Redescribed and neotype (from Bennachie, Little Oxen Craig, Scotland) designated by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b (original type localities Killin (Scotland), Notteryd (Sweden), Mecklenburg (Germany))>

Guidettion vexatum (Pilato, Sabella, D'Urso & Lisi, 2017) <Transferred from *Adropion* by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020a> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b}

Insulobius Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2020 {1 species}

{The genus described in Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2020a, Supporting Information}

Insulobius orientalis Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2020

Itaquascon de Barros, 1939 {12 species}

<Amended by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020a and by Massa *et al.* 2021>

Itaquascon biserovi Pilato, Binda & Moncada, 1999

Itaquascon cambewarrensense Pilato, Binda & Claxton, 2002

Itaquascon enckelli (Mihelčič, 1971/72) {*nomen dubium* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b}

Itaquascon magnussoni Massa, Guidetti, Cesari, Rebecchi & Jönsson, 2021
Itaquascon mongolicus Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Węglarska, 2002
Itaquascon pilatoi Lisi, Londoño & Quiroga, 2014
Itaquascon pisoniae Pilato & Lisi, 2009
Itaquascon placophorum Maucci, 1973
Itaquascon serratulum Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2024 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b}
Itaquascon simplex (Mihelčič, 1971) {*nomen dubium* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b}
Itaquascon umbellinae de Barros, 1939
Itaquascon unguiculum Pilato, Binda & Claxton, 2002

Mesocrista Pilato, 1987 {2 3 species}

Mesocrista ojagwaji Dobles & Gąsiorek, 2026

Mesocrista revelata Gąsiorek, Stec, Morek, Zawierucha, Kaczmarek, Lachowska-Cierlik & Michalczyk, 2016

Mesocrista spitzbergensis (Richters, 1903) <Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2016>

Parascon Pilato & Binda, 1987 {2 species}

Parascon nichollsae Pilato & Lisi, 2004

Parascon schusteri Pilato & Binda, 1987

Platicrista Pilato, 1987 {12 species}

[*Meplitumen* Lisi, Daza, Londoño, Quiroga & Pilato, 2019 according to Tumanov & Tsvetkova 2023]

<Amended by Scheirer *et al.* 2024 and Gąsiorek 2025>

Platicrista affine (Mihelčič, 1951) {Objectively invalid according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b}

Platicrista aluna (Lisi, Daza, Londoño, Quiroga & Pilato, 2019) <Transferred from *Meplitumen* by Tumanov & Tsvetkova 2023>

Platicrista angustata (Murray, 1905) <Redescribed and neotype (from Hill of Foudland, Scotland) designated by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b (original type locality Loch Ness shore, Scotland)>

Platicrista borneensis Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2024 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b}

Platicrista brunsoni Miller & J.D. Miller, 2021 <Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b based on material from Wyoming, USA (original type locality in Montana, USA)>

Platicrista carpathica Gąsiorek, 2024 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b}

Platicrista cheleusis Kathman, 1990 [*Diphascon craigi* Beasley, 1990]

Platicrista horribilis Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2003 <Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b based on material from Montenegro (original type locality in Mongolia)>

Platicrista itaquasconoide (Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1975) <Transferred from *Platicrista* to *Meplitumen* by Massa *et al.* 2021; Re-transferred from *Meplitumen* by Tumanov & Tsvetkova 2023> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b}

Platicrista loloensis Scheirer, Miller & J.D. Miller, 2024

Platicrista nivea Gąsiorek, 2024 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b}

Platicrista ramsayi Marley, 2006

Raribius Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2020 {3 species}

{The genus described in Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2020a, Supporting Information}

Raribius globuliferus (Abe & Ito, 1994) <Transferred from *Itaquascon* by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020a>

Raribius minutissimus Gąsiorek & Michalczyk, 2024 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b}

Raribius pawlowskii (Węglarska, 1973) <Transferred from *Itaquascon* by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020a>

Sarascon Guil, Rodrigo & Machordom, 2014 {1 species}

Sarascon hortensiae Guil, Rodrigo & Machordom, 2014

Family: Microhypsibiidae Pilato, 1998 {2 genera}

<Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019c>

Fractonotus Pilato, 1998 {1 species}

<Amended and transferred from Microhypsibiidae to Isohypsibiidae by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019c;

Re-transferred to Microhypsibiidae by Bertolani 2024>

Fractonotus caelatus (Marcus, 1928)

Microhypsibius Thulin, 1928 {4 species}

Microhypsibius bertolanii Kristensen, 1982

Microhypsibius japonicus Ito, 1991

Microhypsibius minimus Kristensen, 1982

Microhypsibius truncatus Thulin, 1928

Family: Pilatobiidae Bertolani, Guidetti, Marchioro, Altiero, Rebecchi & Cesari, 2014 {4 genera}

<Amended by Gąsiorek & Michalczyk 2020a; Elevated from the subfamily level in Hypsibiidae by Tumanov & Tsvetkova 2023 however, Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b do not recognized the validity of this proposal>

Degmion Gąsiorek, Morek & Michalczyk, 2024 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b} {6 species}

Degmion burti (Nelson, 1991) <Transferred from *Diphascon* to *Pilatobius* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Transferred from *Pilatobius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>

Degmion nodulosum (Ramazzotti, 1957) <Transferred from *Diphascon* to *Pilatobius* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Transferred from *Pilatobius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>

Degmion nuominense (X.-L. Sun, J.-Y. Zhang, N. Wang, M. Zhao & Luo, 2021) <Transferred from *Pilatobius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>

Degmion oculatum (Murray, 1906) <Transferred from *Diphascon* to *Pilatobius* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Transferred from *Pilatobius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b; Redescribed and neotype (from Oxen Craig, Aberdeenshire, Scotland, UK) designated by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b (original type locality Hopetoun Wood, Broxburn, Scotland, UK); *Pilatobius oculatus alpium* (Mihelčič, 1964) {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015} and *Pilatobius oculatus canadensis* (Murray, 1910) {*nomen dubium* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b} [synonym *Hypsibius vancouverensis* Thulin, 1911] - both transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014 and suppressed by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>

Degmion opisthoglyptum (Maucci, 1987) <Transferred from *Diphascon* to *Pilatobius* by Tumanov 2018; Transferred from *Pilatobius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>

Degmion rugocaudatum (Rodriguez Roda, 1952) <Transferred from *Diphascon* to *Pilatobius* by

Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Transferred from *Pilatobius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b}

Fontourion Gąsiorek, Morek & Michalczyk, 2024 {in Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b} {6 species}

Fontourion boreale (Biserov, 1996) <Transferred from *Diphascon* to *Pilatobius* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Transferred from *Pilatobius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>

Fontourion brevipes (Marcus, 1936) <Transferred from *Diphascon* to *Pilatobius* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Transferred from *Pilatobius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>

Fontourion glaciale (Zawierucha, Buda & Gąsiorek, 2020) {in Zawierucha *et al.* 2020} <Transferred from *Pilatobius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>

Fontourion islandicum (Buda & Zawierucha, 2018) {in Buda *et al.* 2018} <Transferred from *Pilatobius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>

Fontourion recamierei (Richters, 1911) <Transferred from *Diphascon* to *Pilatobius* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2017a; Transferred from *Pilatobius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>

Fontourion secchii (Bertolani & Rebecchi, 1996) <Transferred from *Diphascon* to *Pilatobius* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Transferred from *Pilatobius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2017a}

Notahypsibius Tumanov, 2020 {3 species}

Notahypsibius arcticus (Murray, 1907) [*Macrobiotus heinisi* Richters, 1907] <Transferred from *Hypsibius* to *Ramazzottius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2018a; transferred from *Ramazzottius* by Tumanov 2020b>

Notahypsibius pallidoides (Pilato, Kiosya, Lisi, Inshina & Biserov, 2011) <Amended and transferred from *Hypsibius* by Tumanov 2020b>

Notahypsibius scaber (Maucci, 1987) <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Tumanov 2020b>

Pilatobius Bertolani, Guidetti, Marchioro, Altiero, Rebecchi & Cesari, 2014 {15 species} <Amended by Tumanov 2020b>

Pilatobius aculeatus (Maucci, 1951-1952) <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014>

Pilatobius bisbullatus (Iharos, 1964) <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014>

Pilatobius bullatus (Murray, 1905) [*Pilatobius trachydorsatus* (Bartoš, 1937), previously transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014, synonym according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b] <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b>

Pilatobius elongatus (Mihelčič, 1959) {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyč 2015} <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014>

Pilatobius gerdae (Mihelčič, 1951) <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014> {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyč 2015}

Pilatobius granifer (Greven, 1972) <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014>

Pilatobius iltisi (Schuster & Grigarick, 1965) <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2024b based on material from North Korea and Russia (original type localities in California, USA)>

Pilatobius latipes (Mihelčič, 1955) <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014> {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyč 2015}

Pilatobius nonbullatus (Mihelčič, 1951) <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014>
{*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015}
Pilatobius patanei (Binda & Pilato, 1971) <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.*
2014>
Pilatobius procerus (Pilato, Sabella & Lisi, 2014) <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Tumanov
2018>
Pilatobius ramazzottii (Robotti, 1970) <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014>
Pilatobius rugosus (Bartoš, 1935) <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014>
Pilatobius sexbullatus (Ito, 1995) <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014>
Pilatobius ziliense (Lisi, Sabella & Pilato, 2014) <Transferred from *Diphascon* by Tumanov
2018>

Family: Ramazzottiidae Sands, McInnes, Marley, Goodall-Copestake, Convey & Linse, 2008 {3
genera}
{Sands *et al.* 2008 reported as taxon name Ramazzottidae but the correct name is Ramazzottiidae
in compliance with the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature}

Cryoconicus Zawierucha, Stec, Lachowska-Cierlik, Takeuchi, Z. Li & Michalczyk, 2018 {4
species}
<Amended by Guidetti *et al.* 2019b>

Cryoconicus antiarktos Guidetti, Massa, Bertolani, Rebecchi & Cesari, 2019
Cryoconicus cataphractus (Maucci, 1974) <Transferred from *Ramazzottius* by Zawierucha *et al.*
2018b; Amended by Guidetti *et al.* 2019b>
Cryoconicus kaczmareki Zawierucha, Stec, Lachowska-Cierlik, Takeuchi, Z. Li & Michalczyk,
2018
Cryoconicus ljudmilae (Biserov, 1997/98) <Amended and transferred from *Ramazzottius* by
Guidetti *et al.* 2019b>

Hebesuncus Pilato, 1987 {4 species}

Hebesuncus conjugens (Thulin, 1911)
Hebesuncus mollispinus Pilato, McInnes & Lisi, 2012
Hebesuncus ryani Dastych & Harris, 1994 <Amended by Guidetti *et al.* 2019b>
Hebesuncus schusteri (Dastych, 1984)

Ramazzottius Binda & Pilato, 1986 {~~32~~ 33 species}

Ramazzottius affinis Bertolani, Guidetti & Rebecchi, 1994
Ramazzottius agannae Dastych, 2011
Ramazzottius andreevi Biserov, 1997/98
Ramazzottius anomalus (Ramazzotti, 1962)
Ramazzottius baumanni (Ramazzotti, 1962)
Ramazzottius belubellus Bartels, Nelson, Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2011
Ramazzottius bunikowskiae Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Diduszko, 2006
Ramazzottius caucasicus Biserov, 1997/98
Ramazzottius claudii Vecchi & Stec, 2024
Ramazzottius conifer (Mihelčič, 1938) <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2018a>
Ramazzottius edmondabouti Séméria, 1993 {*species dubia* according to Guidetti *et al.* 2022a}

Ramazzottius groenlandensis Kihm, Zawierucha, Rho & Park, 2023
Ramazzottius horningi Binda & Pilato, 1994
Ramazzottius kretschmanni Guidetti, Cesari, Giovannini, Ebel, Förschler & Schill, 2022
Ramazzottius libycus Pilato, D'Urso & Lisi, 2013
Ramazzottius littoreus Fontoura, Rubal & Veiga, 2017
Ramazzottius montivagus (Dastyh, 1983)
Ramazzottius nivalis Dastyh, 2006 <Amended by Guidetti *et al.* 2019b>
Ramazzottius novemcinctus (Marcus, 1936) {*nomen dubium* according to Stec *et al.* 2018}
Ramazzottius oberhaeuseri (Doyère, 1840) <Amended by Stec *et al.* 2018>
Ramazzottius rupeus Biserov, 1999
Ramazzottius sabatiniae Guidetti, Massa, Bertolani, Rebecchi & Cesari, 2019
Ramazzottius saltensis (Claps & Rossi, 1984)
Ramazzottius semisculptus Pilato & Rebecchi, 1992
Ramazzottius subanomalous (Biserov, 1985)
Ramazzottius suzithuae Romero-Mendoza, Brandoli, Guidetti, Vincenzi, Hernández-Mena, Cesari, Mata-López & Rivas, 2026
Ramazzottius syraxi Polishchuk, Kayastha, Warguła & Kaczmarek, 2025 {in Polishchuk *et al.* 2025}
Ramazzottius szeptycki (Dastyh, 1980) <Amended by Dastyh 2009>
Ramazzottius theroni Dastyh, 1993
Ramazzottius thulini (Pilato, 1970)
Ramazzottius tribulosus Bertolani & Rebecchi, 1988
Ramazzottius valaamis Biserov & Tumanov, 1993
Ramazzottius varieornatus Bertolani & Kinchin, 1993

Incerta familia {according to Mapalo *et al.* 2024}

{The following genus is placed in Hypsibioidea but outside families of the superfamily, see Mapalo *et al.* 2024}

Aerobius Mapalo, Wolfe & Ortega-Hernández, 2024 {1 species}

Aerobius dactylus Mapalo, Wolfe & Ortega-Hernández, 2024 {fossil species}

Superfamily: Isohypsibioidea Sands, McInnes, Marley, Goodall-Copestake, Convey & Linse, 2008 {5 families}

<Amended by Bertolani *et al.* 2014 and by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Family: Doryphoribiidae Gąsiorek, Stec, Morek & Michalczyk, 2019 {7 genera}

Apodibius Dastyh, 1983 {3 2 species}

<Transferred from '*incertae sedis*' to Isohypsibidae by Dabert *et al.* 2013; Transferred from Isohypsibidae by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Apodibius confusus Dastyh, 1983

~~*Apodibius muntius*~~ Binda, 1984 [~~*Apodibius serventyi*~~ Morgan & Nicholls, 1986] {see *Sinunguibius*, Hexapodibiidae}

Apodibius richardi Vargha, 1995

Doryphoribius Pilato, 1969 {42 species}
 <Transferred from Isohypsibiidae by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Doryphoribius amazonicus Lisi, 2011
Doryphoribius barbarae Beasley & Miller, 2012
Doryphoribius bertolanii Beasley & Pilato, 1987
Doryphoribius bindae Lisi, 2011
Doryphoribius cephalogibbosus Rocha, Doma, Gonzales Reyes & Lisi, 2020
Doryphoribius chetumalensis Pérez-Pech, Anguas-Escalante, Cutz-Pool & Guidetti, 2017
Doryphoribius dawkinsi Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2010
Doryphoribius doryphorus (Binda & Pilato, 1969)
Doryphoribius dupliglobulatus Ito, 1995
Doryphoribius elleneddiei Haefke, Spiers, Miller & Lowman, 2014
Doryphoribius evelinae (Marcus, 1928)
Doryphoribius flavus (Iharos, 1966) [*Doryphoribius citrinus* (Maucci, 1973)] <Amended by Lisi 2011>
Doryphoribius gibber Beasley & Pilato, 1987 {Based on type material analysis, additional character to the original description was added by Pilato & Lisi 2006}
Doryphoribius huangguoshuensis H. Wang, L. Wang & X. Li, 2007
Doryphoribius koreanus Moon, W. Kim & Bertolani, 1994
Doryphoribius korganovae Biserov, 1994
Doryphoribius longistipes Bartels, Nelson, Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2008
Doryphoribius macrodon Binda, Pilato & Dastych, 1980
Doryphoribius maasaimarensis Fontoura, Lisi & Pilato, 2013
Doryphoribius maranguensis Binda & Pilato, 1995
Doryphoribius mariae Pilato & Binda, 1990
Doryphoribius mcinnesae Meng, X.-Z. Sun & X. Li, 2014
Doryphoribius mexicanus Beasley, Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2008
Doryphoribius minimus Bartels, Nelson, Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2008
Doryphoribius monstruosus (Maucci, 1991) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Doryphoribius neglectus Pilato & Lisi, 2004
Doryphoribius niedbalai Zawierucha, Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2012
Doryphoribius picoensis Fontoura, Pilato & Lisi, 2008
Doryphoribius pilatoi Bertolani, 1984
Doryphoribius polynettae Biserov, 1988
Doryphoribius qinlingense X. Li, Su & Yu, 2004
Doryphoribius quadrituberculatus Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2004
Doryphoribius rosanae Daza, Caicedo, Lisi & Quiroga, 2017
Doryphoribius smokiensis Bartels, Nelson, Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2007
Doryphoribius solidunguis Lisi, 2011
Doryphoribius taiwanus X. Li & H. Li, 2008
Doryphoribius tergumrudis Bartels, Nelson, Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2008
Doryphoribius tessellatus Meyer, 2011
Doryphoribius turkmenicus Biserov, 1999
Doryphoribius vietnamensis (Iharos, 1969)
Doryphoribius zappalai Pilato, 1971

Doryphoribius zyxiglobus (Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978) <Amended by Claxton *et al.* 2010>

Grevenius Gąsiorek, Stec, Morek & Michalczyk, 2019 {34 35 species}

Grevenius asper (Murray, 1906) [*Isohypsibius tetradactyloides* (Richters, 1907)] <Dastyh 2016 amended *I. tetradactyloides* and synonymized it with *I. asper*; Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius baicalensis (Ramazzotti, 1966) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius baldii (Ramazzotti, 1945) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius baldioides (Tumanov, 2003) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius brevitubulatus (Rho, Chang & W. Kim, 1997) {in Rho *et al.* 1997} <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius cryophilus Zawierucha, Buda, Novotna Jaromerska & Gąsiorek, 2020 {in Zawierucha *et al.* 2020}

Grevenius deconincki (Pilato, 1971) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius deflexus (Mihelčič, 1960) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius fuscus (Mihelčič, 1971/72) {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e} <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius granditintinus (Chang & Rho, 1996) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius granulifer (Thulin, 1928) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e; Redescribed by Gąsiorek 2024 based on topotypic population>

Grevenius hydrogogianus (Ito & Tagami, 1993) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius karenae (Zawierucha, 2013) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius kenodontis (Kendall-Fite & Nelson, 1996) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius koreanensis (Iharos, 1971) <*Isohypsibius granulifer koreanensis* elevated to species level and transferred by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Grevenius kotovae (Tumanov, 2003) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius kristenseni (Pilato, Catanzaro & Binda, 1989) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius ladogensis (Tumanov, 2003) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius laevis (McInnes, 1995) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius lineatus (Mihelčič, 1969) {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyh 2015; *nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e} <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius longiunguis (Pilato, 1974) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius malawiensis (Jørgensen, 2001) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius marii (Bertolani, 1982) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Grevenius monoicus (Bertolani, 1982) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Grevenius myrops (du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1944) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Grevenius nipponicus (Sudzuki, 1975) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Grevenius occultus (Pilato, D'Urso, Sabella & Lisi, 2019) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Tumanov *et al.* 2026>
Grevenius pulcher (Mihelčič, 1971/72) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Grevenius pushkini (Tumanov, 2003) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Grevenius rugosus (Guidi & Grabowski, 1996) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Grevenius rusticus (Pilato, Sabella & Lisi, 2015) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Grevenius sismicus (Maucci, 1978) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Grevenius tuberculatus (Pilato & Catanzaro, 1989) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Grevenius verae (Pilato & Catanzaro, 1989) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Grevenius zappalai (Pilato, Sabella & Lisi, 2015) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Paradiphascon Dastych, 1992 {1 species}

<Transferred from Diphasconinae to Isohypsibiidae by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Transferred from Isohypsibiidae by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Paradiphascon manningi Dastych, 1992

Paradoryphoribius Mapalo, Robin, Boudinot, Ortega-Hernández & Barden, 2021 {1 species}

Paradoryphoribius chronocaribbeus Mapalo, Robin, Boudinot, Ortega-Hernández & Barden, 2021 {fossil species}

Pseudobiotus Nelson, 1980 {in Schuster *et al.* 1980} {7 species}

<Transferred from Isohypsibiidae by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Pseudobiotus hirsutellus Pilato, Lisi & Binda, 2010

Pseudobiotus kathmanae Nelson, Marley & Bertolani, 1999

Pseudobiotus longiunguis (Iharos, 1968) {*species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Pseudobiotus matici (Pilato, 1971)

Pseudobiotus megalonyx (Thulin, 1928)

Pseudobiotus spinifer Chang, Kaczmarek, J.M. Lee & Michalczyk, 2007

Pseudobiotus vladimiri Biserov, Dudichev & Biserova, 2001 <Amended by Chang *et al.* 2007>

Thulinus Bertolani, 2003 {7 species}

[*Thulinia* Bertolani, 1982]

<Transferred from Isohypsibiidae by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Thulinus augusti (Murray, 1907) [*Macrobiotus lacustris* Wenck, 1914] {Murray (1907) used the name *Macrobiotus augusti* in the text, but finally the name *M. augusti* in Fig. 25. Marcus

(1928, p. 194) as the “First Reviser“ of the species (*sensu* ICZN, Art. 24.2.3.) selected *Macrobotus augusti* as the valid name, while *M. angusti* must be considered an erroneous name}

Thulinus gustavi Massa, Guidetti, Cesari, Rebecchi & Jönsson, 2021

Thulinus itoi (Tsurusaki, 1980)

Thulinus romanoi Bertolani, Bartels, Guidetti, Cesari & Nelson, 2014

Thulinus ruffoi (Bertolani, 1982)

Thulinus saltursus (Schuster, Toftner & Grigarick, 1978) <Amended and transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Kaczmarek *et al.* 2010>

Thulinus stephaniae (Pilato, 1974)

Family: Halobiotidae Gąsiorek, Stec, Morek & Michalczyk, 2019 {1 genus}
<Amended by Tumanov *et al.* 2026>

Halobiotus Kristensen, 1982 {5 species}

<Transferred from Isohypsibiidae by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Halobiotus appelloefi (Richters, 1908) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
{*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e and Tumanov *et al.* 2026}

Halobiotus arcturulus Crisp & Kristensen, 1983 <Amended by Tumanov *et al.* 2026>

Halobiotus crispae Kristensen, 1982 <Amended by Tumanov *et al.* 2026>

Halobiotus geddesi (Hallas, 1971) {Petelina & Tchesunov (1983) consider it a synonym of *H. appelloefi*} <Transferred from *Hypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e and Tumanov *et al.* 2026}

Halobiotus stenostomus (Richters, 1908) {*nomen inquirendum* according to Tumanov *et al.* 2026}

Family: Hexapodibiidae Cesari, Vecchi, Palmer, Bertolani, Pilato, Rebecchi & Guidetti, 2016 {4
5 genera}

<Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e and Warguła *et al.* 2025c>

Haplohexapodibius Pilato & Beasley, 1987 {1 species}

<Transferred from Calohypsibiidae to Isohypsibiidae by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Transferred from Isohypsibiidae by Cesari *et al.* 2016>

Haplohexapodibius seductor Pilato & Beasley, 1987 [*Hexapodibius beasleyi* Maucci, 1988]

Haplomacrobotus May, 1948 {2 species}

<Transferred from Calohypsibiidae to Isohypsibiidae by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Transferred from Isohypsibiidae by Cesari *et al.* 2016>

Haplomacrobotus hermosillensis May, 1948

Haplomacrobotus utahensis Pilato & Beasley, 2005

Hexapodibius Pilato, 1969 {6 species}

<Transferred from Calohypsibiidae to Isohypsibiidae by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Transferred from Isohypsibiidae by Cesari *et al.* 2016>

Hexapodibius bindae Pilato, 1982

Hexapodibius boothi Dastyh & McInnes, 1994

Hexapodibius christenberryae Pilato & Binda, 2003

Hexapodibius micronyx Pilato, 1969

Hexapodibius pseudomicronyx Robotti, 1972

Hexapodibius reginae Vargha, 1995

Parhexapodibius Pilato, 1969 {5 species}

<Transferred from Calohypsibiidae to Isohypsibiidae by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Transferred from Isohypsibiidae by Cesari *et al.* 2016>

Parhexapodibius bactrianus Biserov, 1999

Parhexapodibius castrii (Ramazzotti, 1964)

Parhexapodibius lagrecai (Binda & Pilato, 1969)

Parhexapodibius pilato (Bernard, 1977)

Parhexapodibius ramazzottii Manicardi & Bertolani, 1987

Sinunguibius Warguła, Dmuchowska, Stec & Kaczmarek, 2025 {1 species}

Sinunguibius nuntius (Binda, 1984) [*Apodibius serventyi* Morgan & Nicholls, 1986 according to Van Rompu *et al.* 1995] <Transferred from *Apodibius* by Warguła *et al.* 2025c>

Family: Isohypsibiidae Sands, McInnes, Marley, Goodall-Copstake, Convey & Linse, 2008 {9 genera}

<Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Chilibius Tumanov, Shunatova & Fedyuk, 2025 {1 species}

{The genus described in Tumanov *et al.* 2025, Supporting Information}

Chilibius sculptus (Ramazzotti, 1962) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Tumanov *et al.* 2025>

Cucumibius Tumanov, Shunatova & Fedyuk, 2025 {1 species}

{The genus described in Tumanov *et al.* 2025, Supporting Information}

Cucumibius annulatus (Murray, 1905) [*Grevenius annulatus minor* (Ramazzotti, 1945)

transferred from *Isohypsibius* to *Grevenius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e and synonymized by Tumanov *et al.* 2025] <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* to *Grevenius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e; Transferred from *Grevenius* by Tumanov *et al.* 2025>

Dastychius Pilato, 2013 {1 species}

Dastychius improvisus (Dastych, 1984) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Pilato 2013; Amended by Mioduchowska *et al.* 2021>

*Diane*a Gąsiorek, Stec, Morek & Michalczyk, 2019 {16 species}

*Diane*a *acuminata* Gąsiorek, Stec, Morek & Michalczyk, 2019 {This species correspond to *Isohypsibius papillifer indicus* (Iharos, 1969) elevated to species level and renamed by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e as the name *Diane*a *indica* was already occupied by *Diane*a *indica* (Murray, 1907)}

*Diane*a *basalovoi* (Durante & Maucci, 1973) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

*Diane*a *bella* (Mihelčič, 1971) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015; *species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Dianeae belliformis (Mihelčič, 1971) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015; *species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Dianeae brevispinosa (Iharos, 1966) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Dianeae costata (Mihelčič, 1971) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015; *species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Dianeae effusa (Mihelčič, 1971) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015; *species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Dianeae franzi (Mihelčič, 1951) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015; *species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Dianeae helenae (Iharos, 1964) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Dianeae indica (Murray, 1907) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Dianeae mammillosa (Iharos, 1964) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Dianeae papillifera (Murray, 1905) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e; *Isohypsibius papillifer bulbosus* (Marcus, 1928) suppressed by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Dianeae rahmi (X. Li & L. Wang, 2006) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Dianeae sattleri (Richters, 1902) [*Hypsibius bakonyiensis* Iharos, 1964] <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Dianeae tuberculoides (Mihelčič, 1951) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015; *species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Dianeae vej dovskyi (Bartoš, 1939) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Eremobiotus Biserov, 1992 {3 species}
<Amended by Camarda *et al.* 2024>

Eremobiotus alicatai (Binda, 1969) <Redescribed by Camarda *et al.* 2024 based on type material and a new topotypic population>

Eremobiotus ginevrae Lisi, Binda & Pilato, 2016 <Amended by Camarda *et al.* 2024 based on type material>

Eremobiotus ovezovae Biserov, 1992

Isohypsibius Thulin, 1928 {43 42 species}
<Amended by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Isohypsibius arbiter Binda, 1980

Isohypsibius archangajensis Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2004

Isohypsibius arcuatus (Bartoš, 1934)

Isohypsibius barbarae Pilato & Binda, 2002

Isohypsibius borkini Tumanov, 2003
Isohypsibius brulloi Pilato & Pennisi, 1976
Isohypsibius cambrensis (Morgan, 1976) <*I. prosostomus cambrensis* elevated to species level by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Isohypsibius campbellensis Pilato, 1996
Isohypsibius canadensis (Murray, 1910) {*species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Isohypsibius ceciliae Pilato & Binda, 1987
Isohypsibius changbaiensis T. Yang, 1999 {*species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Isohypsibius chiarae Maucci, 1987 [*Isohypsibius bertolanii* Manicardi, 1989]
Isohypsibius condorcanquii Kaczmarek, Cytan, Zawierucha, Diduszko & Michalczyk, 2014
Isohypsibius coulsoni Kaczmarek, Zawierucha, Smykla & Michalczyk, 2012
Isohypsibius damxungensis T. Yang, 2007 {*species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Isohypsibius dastychi Pilato, Bertolani & Binda, 1982
Isohypsibius gilvus Biserov, 1986 <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* to *Fractonotus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019c; Re-transferred to *Isohypsibius* by Bertolani 2024>
Isohypsibius glazovi Biserov, 1999
Isohypsibius hadzii (Mihelčič, 1938) {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyč 2015; *species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Isohypsibius jakieli Dastyč, 1984
Isohypsibius jingshanensis T. Yang, 2003 {*species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Isohypsibius jinhouensis T. Yang, 2007 {*species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Isohypsibius liae X. Li & L. Wang, 2006 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Isohypsibius macrodactylus (Maucci, 1978) [*Isohypsibius zierhofferi* Dastyč, 1980]
Isohypsibius marcellinoi Binda & Pilato, 1971
Isohypsibius occultus Pilato, D'Urso, Sabella & Lisi, 2019 {see *Grevenius*}
Isohypsibius palmae Pilato, 1996
Isohypsibius panovi Tumanov, 2005
Isohypsibius pauper (Mihelčič, 1971) {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyč 2015; *nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Isohypsibius prosostomus Thulin, 1928
Isohypsibius pseudundulatus (da Cunha & do Nascimento Ribeiro, 1964)
Isohypsibius reticulatus Pilato, 1973
Isohypsibius sabellai Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2004
Isohypsibius schaudinni (Richters, 1909) {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Isohypsibius sellnicki (Mihelčič, 1962) {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyč 2015}
Isohypsibius solidus (Mihelčič, 1971) {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyč 2015}
Isohypsibius taibaiensis X. Li & L. Wang, 2005
Isohypsibius tuberculatus (Plate, 1888) {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyč 2015; *nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Isohypsibius undulatus Thulin, 1928
Isohypsibius verrucosus (Della Valle, 1915) [*Isohypsibius gibbus* (Marcus, 1928) according to Degma & Guidetti 2007] {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Isohypsibius verrucosus (Richters, 1900) [*Macrobotus scabrosus* Murray, 1911 according to Marcus 1928, *Calohypsibius placophorus* (da Cunha, 1943) according to Gąsiorek *et al.*

2019c] <Amended and transferred from *Calohypsibius* to *Fractonotus* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019c; Transferred to *Isohypsibius* by Bertolani 2024> {A short article concerning homonymy of both species is ready for publication}

Isohypsibius wilsoni (Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978)

Isohypsibius yunnanensis T. Yang, 2002 {*species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Ursulinius Gąsiorek, Stec, Morek & Michalczyk, 2019 {36 species}

Ursulinius austriacus (Iharos, 1966) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Ursulinius bartosi (Iharos, 1966) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Ursulinius bulbifer (Mihelčič, 1957) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyk 2015; *species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Ursulinius cameruni (Iharos, 1969) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Ursulinius cyrilli (Mihelčič, 1951) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyk 2015}

Ursulinius dudichi (Iharos, 1964) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Ursulinius duranteae (Maucci, 1978) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Ursulinius elegans (Binda & Pilato, 1971) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Ursulinius eplenyiensis (Iharos, 1970) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Ursulinius glaber (Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1979) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Ursulinius gracilis (Iharos, 1966) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Ursulinius gyulai (Mihelčič, 1971) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyk 2015; *species dubia* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Ursulinius hypostomoides (Mihelčič, 1971) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyk 2015}

Ursulinius josephi (Iharos, 1964) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Ursulinius latiunguis (Iharos, 1964) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Ursulinius leithaicus (Iharos, 1966) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Ursulinius lunulatus (Iharos, 1966) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Ursulinius mihelcici (Iharos, 1964) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Ursulinius montanus (Mihelčič, 1938) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}

Ursulinius neoundulatus (Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1975) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Ursulinius nodosus (Murray, 1907) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyk 2015}

Ursulinius novaeguineae (Iharos, 1967) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Ursulinius pappi (Iharos, 1966) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Ursulinius pilatoi (Durante Pasa & Maucchi, 1979) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Ursulinius pratensis (Iharos, 1964) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Ursulinius qinlingensis (X. Li, L. Wang & Yu, 2005) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Ursulinius roberti (Biserov, 1996) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Ursulinius ronsisvallei (Binda & Pilato, 1969) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Ursulinius rudescui (Iharos, 1966) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Ursulinius septentrionalis (Thulin, 1928) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Ursulinius silvicola (Iharos, 1966) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Ursulinius theresiae (Iharos, 1964) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e}
Ursulinius torulosus (Mihelčič, 1959) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
 {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015}
Ursulinius truncorum (Iharos, 1964) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Ursulinius tucumanensis (Claps & Rossi, 1984) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>
Ursulinius woodsae (Kathman, 1990) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e>

Vladimirobius Kaczmarek, T. Bartylak & Roszkowska, 2020 {1 species}
Vladimirobius irregibilis (Biserov, 1992) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* to *Grevenius* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> <Transferred from *Grevenius* by Kaczmarek *et al.* 2020a>

Weglarskobius Kaczmarek, T. Bartylak & Roszkowska, 2020 {1 species}
Weglarskobius altai (Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2006) <Transferred from *Isohypsibius* by Kaczmarek *et al.* 2020a>

Family: Ramajendidae Tumanov, 2022 {1 genus}

Ramajendas Pilato & Binda, 1990 {4 species}
 <Transferred from Ramazzottiidae to Isohypsibiidae by Zawierucha *et al.* 2018b; Transferred from Isohypsibiidae to *Incertae sedis* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e; Transferred from *Incertae sedis* by Tumanov 2022>

{Probably belongs to the family Ramazzottiidae according to Bertolani *et al.* 2014}
Ramajendas dastychi Kaczmarek, Janko, Smykla & Michalczyk, 20132014
Ramajendas frigidus Pilato & Binda, 1990
Ramajendas heatwolei Miller, Horning & Dastych, 1995
Ramajendas renaudi (Ramazzotti, 1972)

Incertae sedis

Thalerius Dastych, 2009 {1 species}

<Transferred from Ramazzottiidae to Isohypsibiidae by Zawierucha *et al.* 2018b; Transferred from Isohypsibiidae to *Incertae sedis* by Gąsiorek *et al.* 2019e> {To be confirmed in the family Isohypsibiidae, see Marley *et al.* 2011; Probably belongs to the family Ramazzottiidae according to Bertolani *et al.* 2014}

Thalerius konradi Dastych, 2009

Thulyphoribius Camarda, Lisi, Stec & Vecchi, 2025 {1 species}

<*Incertae sedis* by Camarda *et al.* 2025>

Thulyphoribius melitense Camarda, Lisi, Stec & Vecchi, 2025

Superfamily: Macrobitoidea Thulin, 1928 {in Marley *et al.* 2011} {4 families}

Family: Adorybiotidae Stec, Vecchi & Michalczyk, 2020 {in Stec *et al.* 2020f} {2 genera}

Adorybiotus Maucci & Ramazzotti, 1981 {1 species}

<Transferred from *Macrobiotidae* to Richtersiidae by Guidetti *et al.* 2016; Transferred from Richtersiidae by Stec *et al.* 2020f; Belonging to Richtersiusidae according to Guidetti *et al.* 2021>

Adorybiotus granulatus (Richters, 1903)

Crenubiotus Lisi, Londoño & Quiroga, 2020 {5 6 species}

<Transferred from *Macrobiotidae* to Richtersiidae by Lisi *et al.* 2020; Transferred from Richtersiidae by Stec *et al.* 2020f; Belonging to Richtersiusidae according to Guidetti *et al.* 2021>

Crenubiotus crenulatus (Richters, 1904) [*Macrobiotus dentatus* Binda, 1974] <Redescribed, neotype (from Palabione, Valtellina, Italy) designated and transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Lisi *et al.* 2020; Redescribed and new neotype (from the original type locality Svalbard, Norway) designated by Stec *et al.* 2020f>

Crenubiotus liangshuiensis J.-Y. Zhang, X.-L. Sun, N. Wang, Hao, Ma, N. Zhao, H. Li, M. Zhao & S.-T. Yang, 2024

Crenubiotus meg Camarda, Fontaneto & Stec, 2026 {in Camarda *et al.* 2026}

Crenubiotus revelator Lisi, Londoño & Quiroga, 2020

Crenubiotus ruhesteyni Guidetti, Schill, Giovannini, Massa, Goldoni, Ebel, Förschler, Rebecchi & Cesari, 2021

Crenubiotus salishani Vecchi, Choong & Calhim, 2022

Family: Macrobiotidae Thulin, 1928 {15 genera}

Biserovus Guidetti & Pilato, 2003 {1 species}

Biserovus bindae (Christenberry & Higgins, 1979)

Calcarobiotus Dastych, 1993 {2 subgenera}

Subgenus: *Calcarobiotus* Dastych, 1993 {8 species}

<Amended by Kaczmarek *et al.* 2006>

Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) digeronimoi Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2004
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) filmeri Dastych, 1993
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) gildae (Maucci & Durante Pasa, 1980)
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) hainanensis X. Li, D. Wang & L. Wang, 2008
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) imperialis Abe & Takeda, 2000
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) longinoi Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Guidetti, 2006
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) occultus Dastych, 1993
Calcarobiotus (Calcarobiotus) parvicalcar Pilato & Lisi, 2009

Subgenus: *Discrepunguis* Guidetti & Bertolani, 2001 {2 species}

Calcarobiotus (Discrepunguis) polygonatus (Binda & Guglielmino, 1991) [*Macrobilotus eugranulatus* Maucci, 1993]
Calcarobiotus (Discrepunguis) tetrannulatus Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2004

Famelobiotus Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2004 {1 species}

Famelobiotus scalicii Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2004

Insuetifurca Guidetti & Pilato, 2003 {4 species}

Insuetifurca arrowsmithi (Kathman & Nelson, 1989)

Insuetifurca austronipponica Abe, 2005

Insuetifurca fujiense (Ito, 1997)

Insuetifurca xiae (X. Li, Su & Yu, 2004) <Amended based on holotype and population from Hainan Province, China (original type locality in Zhejiang Province, China) and transferred from *Biserovus* by Li 2009>

Macrobilotus C.A.S. Schultze, 1834 {~~132~~ 140 species + 1 subspecies}

<Amended by Stec *et al.* 2021a>

Macrobilotus acadianus (Meyer & Domingue, 2011) <Transferred from *Minibiotus* by Stec *et al.* 2015>

Macrobilotus almadai Fontoura, Pilato & Lisi, 2008

Macrobilotus alvaroi Pilato & Kaczmarek, 2007

Macrobilotus anderssoni Richters, 1908

Macrobilotus andinus Maucci, 1988

Macrobilotus anemone Meyer, Domingue & Hinton, 2014

Macrobilotus annae Richters, 1908 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}

Macrobilotus annewintersae Vecchi & Stec, 2021

***Macrobilotus anshui* Kayastha, Mioduchowska, Gawlak, Rutkowski, Redgate, Sługocki & Kaczmarek, 2025**

Macrobilotus ariekammensis ariekammensis Węglarska, 1965 [*Macrobilotus adelges* Dastych, 1977]

Macrobilotus ariekammensis groenlandicus Stec, Vončina, Kristensen & Michalczyk, 2022

Macrobilotus artipharyngis Iharos, 1940 {*nomen dubium* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}

Macrobilotus ascensionis Richters, 1908 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}

Macrobilotus azzunae Ben Marnissi, Cesari, Rebecchi & Bertolani, 2021

Macrobilotus basiatus Nelson, Adkins Fletcher, Guidetti, Roszkowska, Grobys & Kaczmarek, ~~2021~~ 2020

Macrobotus birendrai Kayastha, Roszkowska, Mioduchowska, Gawlak & Kaczmarek, 2021
Macrobotus biserovi Bertolani, Guidi & Rebecchi, 1996
Macrobotus brevipes Mihelčič, 1971/72 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus caelestis Coughlan, Michalczyk & Stec, 2019
Macrobotus canaricus Stec, Krzywański & Michalczyk, 2018
Macrobotus carsicus Maucci, 1954 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus caymanensis Meyer, 2011
Macrobotus crustulus Stec, Dudziak & Michalczyk, 2020
Macrobotus dalaticus Stec, 2026
Macrobotus dariae Pilato & Bertolani, 2004
Macrobotus deceptor Meyer, Hinton, Gladney & Klumpp, 2017
Macrobotus denticulus Dastych, 2002
Macrobotus diversus Biserov, 1990
Macrobotus dolosus Bertolani, Cesari, Giovannini, Rebecchi, Guidetti, Kaczmarek & Pilato, 2023
Macrobotus drakensbergi Dastych, 1993
Macrobotus dulciporus Roszkowska, Gawlak, Draga & Kaczmarek, 2019
Macrobotus echinogenitus Richters, 1903
Macrobotus engbergi Stec, Tumanov & Kristensen, 2020
Macrobotus evelinae de Barros, 1938 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus excelsus López-Sandoval & Pérez, 2026
Macrobotus fontourai Bertolani, Cesari, Giovannini, Rebecchi, Guidetti, Kaczmarek & Pilato, 2023
Macrobotus gemmatus Bartoš, 1963 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus glebkai Biserov, 1990
Macrobotus halophilus Fontoura, Rubal & Veiga, 2017
Macrobotus hannaе Nowak & Stec, 2018
Macrobotus hibiscus de Barros, 1942 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus hoianicus Stec, 2026
Macrobotus horningi Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2017
Macrobotus hufelandi C.A.S. Schultze, 1834 [*Macrobotus schultzei* Greeff, 1866 according to Marcus 1928]
Macrobotus humilis Binda & Pilato, 2001
Macrobotus hupingensis Yuan, Y. Wang, Q. Liu, L. Liu & X. Li, 2022
Macrobotus hyperboreus Biserov, 1990
Macrobotus hyperoncus (Meyer, Domingue & Hinton, 2014) <Transferred from *Murrayon* by Guidetti *et al.* 2022b>
Macrobotus ignifer López-Sandoval & Pérez, 2026
Macrobotus iharosi Pilato, Binda & Catanzaro, 1991
Macrobotus insignis Bartoš, 1963 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus insularis Pilato, 2006
Macrobotus joannae Pilato & Binda, 1983
Macrobotus julianae (Meyer, 2012) <Transferred from *Minibiotus* by Stec *et al.* 2015>
Macrobotus kamilae Coughlan & Stec, 2019
Macrobotus kathyae Massa & Vecchi, 2024
Macrobotus kazmierskii Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2009

Macrobotus kirghizicus Tumanov, 2005
Macrobotus kollerii Mihelčič, 1951 {*nomen dubium* according to Dastych 2015; *nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus komareki Bartoš, 1939 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus kosmali Kayastha, Mioduchowska, Gawlak, Sługocki, Araújo, Gonçalves Silva & Kaczmarek, 2023
Macrobotus kristenseni Guidetti, Peluffo, Rocha, Cesari & Moly de Peluffo, 2013
Macrobotus kurasi Dastych, 1981
Macrobotus kyoukenus Cesari, Giovannini, Altiero, Guidetti, Cornette, Kikawada & Rebecchi, 2022
Macrobotus lissostomus Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1979
Macrobotus longipes Mihelčič, 1971/72 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus macrocalix Bertolani & Rebecchi, 1993
Macrobotus maculatus Iharos, 1973 <*M. hufelandi maculatus* amended based on type material and elevated to species level by Kaczmarek & Michalczyk 2017>
Macrobotus madegassus Maucci, 1993
Macrobotus mandalae Pilato, 1974
Macrobotus margoae Stec, Vecchi & Bartels, 2021 {in Stec *et al.* 2021b}
Macrobotus marlenae Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2004
Macrobotus martini Bartels, Pilato, Lisi & Nelson, 2009
Macrobotus mileri Stec, 2024
Macrobotus modestus Pilato & Lisi, 2009
Macrobotus muralis Bertolani, Cesari, Giovannini, Rebecchi, Guidetti, Kaczmarek & Pilato, 2023
Macrobotus naskreckii Bąkowski, Roszkowska, Gawlak & Kaczmarek, 2016
Macrobotus nebrodensis Pilato, Sabella, D'Urso & Lisi, 2017
Macrobotus nelsonae Guidetti, 1998
Macrobotus noemiae Roszkowska & Kaczmarek, 2019
Macrobotus noongaris Coughlan & Stec, 2019
Macrobotus norvegicus Mihelčič, 1971/72 {*nomen dubium* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus occidentalis Dastych, 1974 {Massa *et al.* (2024) proposed the elevation of *Macrobotus occidentalis striatus* Dastych, 1974 to species level, renaming it as *Macrobotus occidentalis* Dastych, 1974 because of validity of *Macrobotus striatus* Mihelčič, 1949}
Macrobotus ocotensis Pilato, 2006
Macrobotus olgae Rocha, Camarda, Doma, Ostertag, González-Reyes, Pappalardo & Lisi, 2024
Macrobotus ovidii Bartoš, 1937 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus ovovillosus Baumann, 1960 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus ovovittatus Stec, 2024
Macrobotus pallarii Maucci, 1954 [*Macrobotus aviglianae* Robotti, 1970] {Incorrectly transferred to *Mesobotus* due to an error during the printing process of Vecchi *et al.* 2016a; corrected in Vecchi *et al.* 2016b}
Macrobotus papei Stec, Kristensen & Michalczyk, 2018
Macrobotus papillosus Iharos, 1963 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus patagonicus Maucci, 1988
Macrobotus paulinae Stec, Smolak, Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2015

Macrobotus persimilis Binda & Pilato, 1972
Macrobotus personatus Biserov, 1990
Macrobotus pisacensis Kaczmarek, Cytan, Zawierucha, Diduszko & Michalczyk, 2014
Macrobotus polonicus Pilato, Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Lisi, 2003
Macrobotus polyopus Marcus, 1928
Macrobotus polypiformis Roszkowska, Ostrowska, Stec, Janko & Kaczmarek, 2017
Macrobotus porifini Kuzdrowska, Mioduchowska, Gawlak, T. Bartylak, A. Kepel, M. Kepel & Kaczmarek, 2021
Macrobotus porteri Rahm, 1931 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus potockii Węglarska, 1968 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus primitivae de Barros, 1942
Macrobotus psephus du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1944
Macrobotus pseudopallarii Stec, Vecchi & Michalczyk, 2021 {in Stec *et al.* 2021b}
Macrobotus punctillus Pilato, Binda & Azzaro, 1990
Macrobotus ragonesei Binda, Pilato, Moncada & Napolitano, 2001
Macrobotus ramoli Dastyk, 2005
Macrobotus rawsoni Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978 <Amended by Kaczmarek & Michalczyk 2017 based on type material>
Macrobotus rebecchii Stec, 2022
Macrobotus recens Cuénot, 1932
Macrobotus ripperi Stec, Vecchi & Michalczyk, 2021 {in Stec *et al.* 2021b}
Macrobotus rollei Heinis, 1920 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus rubens Murray, 1907 {*nomen dubium* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus rybaki Stec & Vecchi, 2021 {in Vecchi & Stec 2021}
Macrobotus sandrae Bertolani & Rebecchi, 1993
Macrobotus santoroi Pilato & D'Urso, 1976
Macrobotus sapiens Binda & Pilato, 1984
Macrobotus scoticus Stec, Morek, Gąsiorek, Blagden & Michalczyk, 2017
Macrobotus semmelweisi Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2006
Macrobotus serratus Bertolani, Guidi & Rebecchi, 1996
Macrobotus seychellensis Biserov, 1994
Macrobotus sharopovi Polishchuk, Kayastha, Młodzianowska, Warguła & Kaczmarek, 2025 {in Polishchuk *et al.* 2025}
Macrobotus shennongensis T. Yang, 1999 {*nomen dubium* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobotus shonaicus Stec, Arakawa & Michalczyk, 2018
Macrobotus siderophilus Bertolani, Cesari, Giovannini, Rebecchi, Guidetti, Kaczmarek & Pilato, 2023
Macrobotus sottilei Pilato, Kiosya, Lisi & Sabella, 2012
Macrobotus stanislausii Kaczmarek, Rutkowski, Zacharyasiewicz, Surmacki, Osiejuk & Kayastha, 2023
Macrobotus striatus Mihelčič, 1949 {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyk 2015; *nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
***Macrobotus surmaczi* Stec, 2026**
Macrobotus terminalis Bertolani & Rebecchi, 1993
Macrobotus terricola Mihelčič, 1951 {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyk 2015; *nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}

Macrobiotus tetraplacoides Fontoura, 1981 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobiotus topali Iharos, 1969 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobiotus trunovae Biserov, Pilato & Lisi, 2011
Macrobiotus vattenrikense Hulterström, Guidetti, Jönsson & Atherton, 2025
Macrobiotus virgatus Murray, 1910 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}
Macrobiotus vladimiri Bertolani, Biserov, Rebecchi & Cesari, 2011
Macrobiotus wandae Kayastha, Berdi, Miaduchowska, Gawlak, Łukasiewicz, Gołdyn & Kaczmarek, 2020
Macrobiotus witalinskii Stec, 2026
Macrobiotus yunshanensis T. Yang, 2002 {*nomen dubium* according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}

Mesobiotus Vecchi, Cesari, Bertolani, Jönsson, Rebecchi & Guidetti, 2016 {84 86 species}
Mesobiotus altitudinalis (Biserov, 1997/98) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus anastasiae Tumanov, 2020
Mesobiotus aradasi (Binda, Pilato & Lisi, 2005) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus arguei (Pilato & Sperlinga, 1975) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus armatus (Pilato & Binda, 1996) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a> {*species inquirenda* according to Roszkowska *et al.* 2017}
Mesobiotus australis (Pilato & D'Urso, 1976) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus baltatus (McInnes, 1991) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus barabanovi (Tumanov, 2005) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus barbarae (Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Degma, 2007) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus binieki (Kaczmarek, Gołdyn, Prokop & Michalczyk, 2011) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus blocki (Dastyk, 1984) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus bockebodicus Atherton, Hulterström, Guidetti & Jönsson, 2025
Mesobiotus contii (Pilato & Lisi, 2006) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus coronatus (de Barros, 1942) <Amended by Pilato *et al.* 2000; Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus creber (Pilato & Lisi, 2009) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus datanlanicus Stec, 2019
Mesobiotus diegoi Stec, 2022
Mesobiotus diffusus (Binda & Pilato, 1987) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus diguensis (Pilato & Lisi, 2009) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus dilimanensis Itang, Stec, Mapalo, Mirano-Bascos & Michalczyk, 2020
Mesobiotus dimentmani (Pilato, Lisi & Binda, 2010) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus divergens (Binda, Pilato & Lisi, 2005) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et*

al. 2016a>
Mesobiotus efa Tumanov, Androsova, Gavrilenko & Kalimullin, 2024
Mesobiotus emiliae Massa, Guidetti, Cesari, Rebecchi & Jönsson, 2021 {Based on type material, additional characters to the original description were added by Atherton *et al.* 2025}
Mesobiotus erminiae (Binda & Pilato, 1999) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus ethiopicus Stec & Kristensen, 2017
Mesobiotus fiedleri Kaczmarek, T. Bartylak, Stec, Kulpa, M. Kepel, A. Kepel & Roszkowska, 2020
Mesobiotus furciger (Murray, 1907) [*Macrobilotus ehrenbergi* Heinis, 1921; *Macrobilotus furcatus* Murray, 1906] <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus harmsworthi (Murray, 1907) [*Mesobiotus harmsworthi obscurus* (Dastych, 1985) according to Kaczmarek *et al.* 2018] <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a; Redescribed by Kaczmarek *et al.* 2018 based on *Macrobilotus harmsworthi obscurus* paratypes>
Mesobiotus helenae Tumanov & Pilato, 2019
Mesobiotus hieronimi (Pilato & Claxton, 1988) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus hilariae Vecchi, Cesari, Bertolani, Jönsson, Rebecchi & Guidetti, 2016a
Mesobiotus huecoensis Vecchi, McDaniel & Walsh, 2023 {in Vecchi *et al.* 2023a}
Mesobiotus getae Stec, 2021
Mesobiotus insanis Mapalo, Stec, Mirano-Bascos & Michalczyk, 2017
Mesobiotus insuetus (Pilato, Sabella & Lisi, 2014) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus joenssoni Guidetti, Gneuss, Cesari, Altiero & Schill, 2020
Mesobiotus kovalevi (Tumanov, 2004) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus krynauwi (Dastych & Harris, 1995) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
***Mesobiotus krystynae* Warguła, Stec, Kayastha, Polishchuk & Kaczmarek, 2025 {in Warguła *et al.* 2025b}**
Mesobiotus liviae (Ramazzotti, 1962) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus longiconicus Dmuchowska, Nawrot, Warguła & Kaczmarek, 2025 {in Dmuchowska *et al.* 2025}
Mesobiotus lusitanicus (Maucci & Durante Pasa, 1984) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus makłowiczi Stec, 2022
Mesobiotus mandalori Erdmann, Kosicki, Kayastha, Mioduchowska & Kaczmarek, 2024
Mesobiotus marmoreus Stec, 2021
Mesobiotus mauccii (Pilato, 1974) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus meridionalis (Richters, 1909) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus montanus (Murray, 1910) [*Macrobilotus morulatus* Bartoš, 1936] <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus mottai (Binda & Pilato, 1994) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>
Mesobiotus neuquensis (Rossi, Claps & Ardohain, 2009) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by

Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus nikolaevae Tumanov, 2018

Mesobiotus nuragicus (Pilato & Sperlinga, 1975) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus occultatus Kaczmarek, Zawierucha, Buda, Stec, Gawlak, Michalczyk & Roszkowska, 2018

Mesobiotus orcadensis (Murray, 1907) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus ovostratus (Pilato & Patanè, 1998) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus patiens (Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2000) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus perfidus (Pilato & Lisi, 2009) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus peterseni (Maucci, 1991) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus philippinicus Mapalo, Stec, Mirano-Bascos & Michalczyk, 2016

Mesobiotus pilatoi (Binda & Rebecchi, 1992) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus polaris (Murray, 1910) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus pseudoblocki Roszkowska, Stec, Ciobanu & Kaczmarek, 2016

Mesobiotus pseudocoronatus (Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2006) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus pseudoliviae (Pilato & Binda, 1996) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus pseudonuragicus (Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2004) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus pseudopatiens Kaczmarek & Roszkowska, 2016

Mesobiotus radiatus (Pilato, Binda & Catanzaro, 1991) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus reinhardti (Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2003) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus rigidus (Pilato & Lisi, 2006) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus romani Roszkowska, Stec, Gawlak & Kaczmarek, 2018

Mesobiotus siamensis (Tumanov, 2006) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus sicheli (Binda, Pilato & Lisi, 2005) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus silesiacus Warguła, Stec, Rutkowski, Kayastha, Gierlasiński & Kaczmarek, 2025 {in Warguła *et al.* 2025a}

Mesobiotus simulans (Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2000) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus skanensis Atherton, Hultström, Guidetti & Jönsson, 2025

Mesobiotus skorackii Kaczmarek, Zawierucha, Buda, Stec, Gawlak, Michalczyk & Roszkowska, 2018

Mesobiotus snaresensis (Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus stellaris (du Bois-Reymond Marcus, 1944) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus szeptyckii (Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2009) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus tehuelchensis (Rossi, Claps & Ardohain, 2009) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus ugandicus Warguła, Stec, Kayastha, Polishchuk & Kaczmarek, 2025 {in Warguła *et al.* 2025b}

Mesobiotus vulpinus Tumanov, Androsova, Gavrilenko & Kalimullin, 2024

Mesobiotus wuzhishanensis (Yin, L. Wang & X. Li, 2011) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Mesobiotus zelmae Atherton, Hulterström, Guidetti & Jönsson, 2025

Mesobiotus zhejiangensis (Yin, L. Wang & X. Li, 2011) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Vecchi *et al.* 2016a>

Minibiotus R.O. Schuster, 1980 {in Schuster *et al.* 1980} {56 57 species}

Minibiotus acontistus (de Barros, 1942)

Minibiotus aculeatus (Murray, 1910) [~~*Macrobotus intermedius subjulietae* Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978~~] {see *M. subjulietae*}

Minibiotus africanus Binda & Pilato, 1995

Minibiotus allani (Murray, 1913)

Minibiotus aquatilis Claxton, 1998

Minibiotus asteris Claxton, 1998

Minibiotus bernhardi R. Schuster, 2021

Minibiotus bisoctus (Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978)

Minibiotus citlalium Dueñas-Cedillo & García-Román, 2020 {in Dueñas-Cedillo *et al.* 2020}

Minibiotus claxtonae Rossi, Claps & Ardohain, 2009

Minibiotus constellatus Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2003

Minibiotus continuus Pilato & Lisi, 2006

Minibiotus crassidens (Murray, 1907)

Minibiotus decrescens Binda & Pilato, 1995

Minibiotus diphasconides (Iharos, 1969)

Minibiotus dispositus Rocha, Doma, Camarda, Ostertag, Meier, Frigieri, Cesari & Lisi, 2024

Minibiotus diversus Ciobanu, Roszkowska & Kaczmarek, 2015

Minibiotus eichhorni Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2004

Minibiotus ethelae Claxton, 1998

Minibiotus fallax Pilato, Claxton & Binda, 1989

Minibiotus floriparus Claxton, 1998

Minibiotus formosus Zawierucha, Dziamięcki, Jakubowska, Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2014

Minibiotus furcatus (Ehrenberg, 1859) [~~*nec Macrobotus furcatus* Murray, 1906~~] <Transferred to *Macrobotus* by Bertolani *et al.* 2014; Re-transferred back to *Minibiotus* by Stec *et al.* 2021a>

Minibiotus granatai (Pardi, 1941)

Minibiotus gumersindoi Guil & Guidetti, 2005

Minibiotus harrylewisi Meyer & Hinton, 2009

Minibiotus hispidus Claxton, 1998

Minibiotus hufelandioides (Murray, 1910)

Minibiotus intermedius (Plate, 1888) <Redescribed and neotype (from Marburg, Germany)

designated by Kaczmarek et al. 2022b (original type locality in Chile and Marburg, Germany)>

Minibiotus ioculator Stec, Kristensen & Michalczyk, 2020

Minibiotus jonesorum Meyer, Lyons, Nelson & Hinton, 2011 {Sumlińska et al. 2026b added new characters to species description}

Minibiotus julietae (de Barros, 1942)

Minibiotus keppelensis Claxton, 1998

Minibiotus lazzaroi (Maucci, 1986) [*Macrobiotus spallanzanii* Maucci, 1973] <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Stec et al. 2021a>

Minibiotus maculartus Pilato & Claxton, 1988

Minibiotus marculsi (de Barros, 1942)

Minibiotus milleri Claxton, 1998

Minibiotus orthofasciatus Fontoura, Pilato, Lisi & Morais, 2009

Minibiotus pentannulatus Londoño, Daza, Lisi & Quiroga, 2017 <Amended by Stec et al. 2020b>

Minibiotus pilatus Claxton, 1998

Minibiotus poricinatus Claxton, 1998

Minibiotus pseudofurcatus (Pilato, 1972) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Stec et al. 2021a>

Minibiotus pseudostellarus Roszkowska, Stec, Ciobanu & Kaczmarek, 2016

Minibiotus pustulatus (Ramazzotti, 1959)

Minibiotus ramazzottii Binda & Pilato, 1992

Minibiotus scopulus Claxton, 1998

Minibiotus sidereus Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2003

Minibiotus spertii (Ramazzotti, 1957) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Stec et al. 2021a>

Minibiotus stuckenbergi (Dastych, Ryan & Watkins, 1990) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Dastych & Drummond 1996>

Minibiotus subintermedius (Ramazzotti, 1962)

Minibiotus subjulietae (Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978) {*Macrobiotus intermedius subjulietae* Horning, Schuster & Grigarick, 1978 synonymized with *Minibiotus aculeatus* by Claxton 1998; valid species according to Sumlińska et al. 2026a}

Minibiotus taiti Claxton, 1998

Minibiotus vinciguerrae Binda & Pilato, 1992

Minibiotus weglarskae Michalczyk, Kaczmarek & Claxton, 2005

Minibiotus weinerorum (Dastych, 1984) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Miller et al. 1994>

Minibiotus wuzhishanensis X. Li, D. Wang & L. Wang, 2008

Minibiotus xavieri Fontoura, Pilato, Morais & Lisi, 2009

Minilentus Guidetti & Pilato, 2003 {1 species}

Minilentus dubius (Schuster & Toftner, 1982)

Paramacrobiotus Guidetti, Schill, Bertolani, Dandekar & Wolf, 2009 {47 49 species}
<Amended by Kaczmarek et al. 2017>

{The genus was split into two subgenera named *Paramacrobiotus* Guidetti et al., 2009 and *Amicrobiotus* Marley et al., 2018 by Kaczmarek et al. 2017 and Marley et al. 2018; The two subgenera are not valid according to Guidetti et al. 2019a}

Paramacrobilotus alekseevi (Tumanov, 2005) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009; Some characters amended by Stec *et al.* 2020e>

Paramacrobilotus arduus Guidetti, Cesari, Bertolani, Altiero & Rebecchi, 2019

Paramacrobilotus areolatus (Murray, 1907) [*Paramacrobilotus crenatus* (Maucci, 1991), previously transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009, according to Stec *et al.* 2020c] <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009; Amended by Stec *et al.* 2020c>

Paramacrobilotus bengalensis Basu, Babu, Siddique & Purushothaman, 2023

Paramacrobilotus beotiae (Durante Pasa & Maucci, 1979) {*species dubia*; Guidetti *et al.* 2009}

Paramacrobilotus bifrons Brandoli, Cesari, Massa, Vecchi, Rebecchi & Guidetti, 2024

Paramacrobilotus celsus Guidetti, Cesari, Bertolani, Altiero & Rebecchi, 2019

Paramacrobilotus centesimus (Pilato, 2000) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobilotus chierегоi (Maucci & Durante Pasa, 1980) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobilotus corgatensis (Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2002) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobilotus csotiensis (Iharos, 1966) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009; Amended by Kaczmarek *et al.* 2017>

Paramacrobilotus danielae (Pilato, Binda, Napolitano & Moncada, 2001) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobilotus danielisae (Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2006) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Degma 2013>

Paramacrobilotus depressus Guidetti, Cesari, Bertolani, Altiero & Rebecchi, 2019

Paramacrobilotus derkai (Degma, Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2008) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobilotus experimentalis Kaczmarek, Mioduchowska, Poprawa & Roszkowska, 2020 {in Kaczmarek *et al.* 2020b}

Paramacrobilotus fairbanksi Schill, Förster, Dandekar & Wolf, 2010 <Amended by Guidetti *et al.* 2019a> {The species had been initially diagnosed based on genetic data only}

Paramacrobilotus filipi Dudziak, Stec & Michalczyk 2020 {in Stec *et al.* 2020e}

Paramacrobilotus gadabouti Kayastha, Stec, Mioduchowska & Kaczmarek, 2023 {in Kayastha *et al.* 2023}

Paramacrobilotus garynahi (Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Diduszko, 2005) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobilotus gerlachae (Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2004) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobilotus halei (Bartels, Pilato, Lisi & Nelson, 2009) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Bartels & Nelson 2012>

Paramacrobilotus hapukuensis (Pilato, Binda & Lisi, 2006) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Degma 2013>

Paramacrobilotus huziori (Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2006) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobilotus intii Kaczmarek, Cytan, Zawierucha, Diduszko & Michalczyk, 2014

Paramacrobotus kenianus Schill, Förster, Dandekar & Wolf, 2010 {The species has been diagnosed based on genetic data only and no morphological difference from *Paramacrobotus richtersi* has been found}

Paramacrobotus klymenki Pilato, Kiosya, Lisi & Sabella, 2012

Paramacrobotus lachowskae Stec, Roszkowska, Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2018

Paramacrobotus lorenae (Biserov, 1996) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobotus magdalenae (Michalczyk & Kaczmarek, 2006) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobotus marchelmoni Hultström, Guidetti, Jönsson & Atherton, 2025

Paramacrobotus mariettae Bordoni, Beretta, Camarda, Stec, Dapporto & Vecchi, 2026

Paramacrobotus metropolitanus Sugiura, Matsumoto & Kunieda, 2022

Paramacrobotus palaui Schill, Förster, Dandekar & Wolf, 2010 {The species has been diagnosed based on genetic data only and no morphological difference from *Paramacrobotus richtersi* has been found}

Paramacrobotus peteri (Pilato, Claxton & Binda, 1989) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobotus pius Lisi, Binda & Pilato, 2016

Paramacrobotus puma López-Sandoval, Montiel-Parra & Pérez, 2025

Paramacrobotus privitera (Binda, Pilato, Moncada & Napolitano, 2001) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Degma 2013>

Paramacrobotus richtersi (Murray, 1911) [*Macrobotus schultzei* Cuénot, 1932 according to Marcus 1936] <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009; Amended by Guidetti *et al.* 2019a>

Paramacrobotus rioplatensis (Claps & Rossi, 1997) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* but doubly attributed to the genus by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobotus sagani Daza, Caicedo, Lisi & Quiroga, 2017

Paramacrobotus savai (Binda & Pilato, 2001) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobotus sklodowskae (Michalczyk, Kaczmarek & Węglarska, 2006) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Degma 2013>

Paramacrobotus spatialis Guidetti, Cesari, Bertolani, Altiero & Rebecchi, 2019

Paramacrobotus spinosus Kaczmarek, Gawlak, Bartels, Nelson & Roszkowska, 2017

Paramacrobotus submorulatus (Iharos, 1966) <Amended and transferred from *Macrobotus* by Kaczmarek *et al.* 2017>

Paramacrobotus tonollii (Ramazzotti, 1956) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobotus vanescens (Pilato, Binda & Catanzaro, 1991) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009> {Based on type material, additional characters to the original description were added by Binda & Pilato 2001 and Pilato *et al.* 2001}

Paramacrobotus walteri (Biserov, 1997/98) <Transferred from *Macrobotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2009>

Paramacrobotus wauensis (Iharos, 1973) <Amended and transferred from *Macrobotus* by Kaczmarek *et al.* 2017> {*nomen dubium* according to Kaczmarek *et al.* 2017}

Pseudodiphascon Ramazzotti, 1965 {*genus dubium* according to Guidetti & Pilato 2003} {1

species}

Pseudodiphascon inflexum (Arcidiacono, 1964)

Pseudohexapodibius Bertolani & Biserov, 1996 {1 species}

Pseudohexapodibius degenerans (Biserov, 1990)

Schusterius Kaczmarek & Michalczyk, 2006 {1 species}

Schusterius tridigitus (R.O. Schuster, 1983)

Sisubiotus Stec, Vecchi, Calhim & Michalczyk, 2021 {4 5 species}
<Amended by Vecchi *et al.* 2022>

Sisubiotus grandis (Richters, 1911) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Stec *et al.* 2021a>
Sisubiotus hakaiensis Vecchi, Choong & Calhim, 2022
Sisubiotus spectabilis (Thulin, 1928) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Stec *et al.* 2021a>
***Sisubiotus splendidus* Atherton, 2025**
Sisubiotus wuyishanensis (P. Zhang & X.-Z. Sun, 2014) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Stec
et al. 2021a> {species inquirenda according to Stec *et al.* 2021a}

Tenuibiotus Pilato & Lisi, 2011 {14 species}
<Amended by Stec & Morek 2022>

Tenuibiotus bondavallii (Manicardi, 1989) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Pilato & Lisi
2011>
Tenuibiotus bozhkae Pilato, Kiosya, Lisi, Inshina & Biserov, 2011
Tenuibiotus ciprianoi (Guil, Guidetti & Machordom, 2007) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by
Pilato & Lisi 2011>
Tenuibiotus danilovi (Tumanov, 2007) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Pilato & Lisi 2011>
Tenuibiotus higginsi (Maucci, 1987) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Pilato & Lisi 2011>
Tenuibiotus hystricogenitus (Maucci, 1978) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Pilato & Lisi
2011>
Tenuibiotus kozharai (Biserov, 1999) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Pilato & Lisi 2011>
Tenuibiotus mongolicus (Maucci, 1988) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Pilato & Lisi 2011>
Tenuibiotus tenuiformis (Tumanov, 2007) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Pilato & Lisi
2011>
Tenuibiotus tenuis (Binda & Pilato, 1972) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Pilato & Lisi
2011>
Tenuibiotus voronkovi (Tumanov, 2007) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Pilato & Lisi 2011;
Amended by Zawierucha *et al.* 2016 and Stec *et al.* 2020d>
Tenuibiotus willardi (Pilato, 1977) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Pilato & Lisi 2011>
Tenuibiotus yeliseii Tsvetkova & Tumanov, 2024
Tenuibiotus zandrae Stec, Tumanov & Kristensen, 2020

Xerobiotus Bertolani & Biserov, 1996 {9 species}
{Proposed to be suppressed with the transfer (for *X. euxinus*, *X. gretae*) and re-transfer (for *X. pseudohufelandi*, *X. xerophilus*) of its species to *Macrobiotus* by Stec *et al.* 2021a, 2022, but
considered valid by Massa *et al.* 2021 and Vincenzi *et al.* 2024}

Xerobiotus arenosum Vincenzi, Cesari, Kaczmarek, Roszkowska, Mioduchowska, Rebecchi,

Kiosya & Guidetti, 2024

- Xerobiotus euxinus* Pilato, Kiosya, Lisi, Inshina & Biserov, 2011 <Transferred from *Xerobiotus* to *Macrobilotus* by Stec et al. 2021a> {Based on type material, additional characters to the original description were added by Vincenzi et al. 2024} <Redescribed by Polishchuk et al. 2024 based on type material and another south Ukrainian population>
- Xerobiotus gretae* Massa, Guidetti, Cesari, Rebecchi & Jönsson, 2021 <Transferred from *Xerobiotus* to *Macrobilotus* by Stec et al. 2022>
- Xerobiotus inermis* (Binda & Pilato, 1971) <*Macrobilotus inermis* Binda & Pilato, 1971 synonymized with *Macrobilotus pseudohufelandi* Iharos, 1966 by Pilato 1973 but considered as *bona species* and transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vincenzi et al. 2024>
- Xerobiotus litus* Vincenzi, Cesari, Kaczmarek, Roszkowska, Mioduchowska, Rebecchi, Kiosya & Guidetti, 2024
- Xerobiotus naginae* (Vecchi, Stec, Vuori, Ryndov, Chartrain & Calhim, 2022) <Transferred from *Macrobilotus* by Vincenzi et al. 2024>
- Xerobiotus pseudohufelandi*** (Iharos, 1966) <Re-transferred from *Xerobiotus* to *Macrobilotus* by Stec et al. 2021a>
- Xerobiotus reductus* Vincenzi, Cesari, Kaczmarek, Roszkowska, Mioduchowska, Rebecchi, Kiosya & Guidetti, 2024
- Xerobiotus xerophilus* (Dastyeh, 1978) <Re-transferred from *Xerobiotus* to *Macrobilotus* by Stec et al. 2021a>

Family: Murrayidae Guidetti, Rebecchi & Bertolani, 2000 {4 genera}

Dactylobiotus R.O. Schuster, 1980 {in Schuster et al. 1980} {19 species}

- Dactylobiotus ambiguus* (Murray, 1907)
- Dactylobiotus ampullaceus* (Thulin, 1911)
- Dactylobiotus aquatilis* T. Yang, 1999 {*nomen dubium* according to Pogwizd & Stec 2020}
- Dactylobiotus caldarellai* Pilato & Binda, 1994 {*nomen dubium* according to Camarda et al. 2025}
- Dactylobiotus dervizi* Biserov, 1998
- Dactylobiotus dispar* (Murray, 1907)
- Dactylobiotus grandipes*** (Schuster, Toftner & Grigarick, 1978) <Amended by Kaczmarek & Michalczyk 2010 based on type material>
- Dactylobiotus haplonyx* Maucci, 1981 {*nomen inquirendum* according to Camarda et al. 2025}
- Dactylobiotus henanensis* T. Yang, 2002 {*nomen dubium* according to Pogwizd & Stec 2020}
- Dactylobiotus kansae* Beasley, Miller & Shively, 2009 {*nomen dubium* according to Pogwizd & Stec 2020}
- Dactylobiotus lombardoi* Binda & Pilato, 1999 {*nomen dubium* according to Camarda et al. 2025}
- Dactylobiotus luci* Kaczmarek, Michalczyk & Eggermont, 2008
- Dactylobiotus macronyx* (Dujardin, 1851) {*nomen dubium* according to Dastyeh 2015 and Pogwizd & Stec 2020}
- Dactylobiotus octavi* Guidetti, Altiero & Hansen, 2006
- Dactylobiotus ovimutans* Kihm, S. Kim, McInnes, Zawierucha, Rho, Kang & Park, 2020
- Dactylobiotus parthenogeneticus* Bertolani, 1982
- Dactylobiotus selenicus* Bertolani, 1982

Dactylobiotus taiwanensis Camarda, Pai, Kristensen & Stec, 2025
Dactylobiotus vulcanus Kaczmarek, Schabetsberger, Litwin & Michalczyk, 2012

Macroversum Pilato & Catanzaro, 1988 {1 species}

Macroversum mirum Pilato & Catanzaro, 1988

Murrayon Bertolani & Pilato, 1988 {4 species}

<Amended by Guidetti *et al.* 2022b>

Murrayon hastatus (Murray, 1907)

Murrayon nocentiniae (Ramazzotti, 1961) {Based on type material, additional characters to the original description were added by Guidetti *et al.* 2022b}

Murrayon ovoglabellus (Biserov, 1988) {Based on type material, additional characters to the original description were added by Guidetti *et al.* 2022b}

Murrayon pullari (Murray, 1907)

Paramurrayon Guidetti, Giovannini, Del Papa, Ekrem, Nelson, Rebecchi & Cesari, 2022 {4 species}

Paramurrayon dianeae (Kristensen, 1982) <Transferred from *Murrayon* by Guidetti *et al.* 2022b>

Paramurrayon hibernicus (Murray, 1911) <Transferred from *Murrayon* by Guidetti *et al.* 2022b> {*nomen dubium* according to Guidetti *et al.* 2022b}

Paramurrayon meieri Guidetti, Giovannini, Del Papa, Ekrem, Nelson, Rebecchi & Cesari, 2022

Paramurrayon stellatus (Guidetti, 1998) <Transferred from *Murrayon* by Guidetti *et al.* 2022b>

Family: Richtersiusidae Guidetti, Schill, Giovannini, Massa, Goldoni, Ebel, Förschler, Rebecchi & Cesari, 2021 {2 genera}

[Richtersiidae Guidetti, Rebecchi, Bertolani, Jönsson, Kristensen & Cesari, 2016 according to Guidetti *et al.* 2021]

<Amended by Lisi *et al.* 2020, Guidetti *et al.* 2021, Stec 2023 and by Massa *et al.* 2024>

Diaforobiotus Guidetti, Rebecchi, Bertolani, Jönsson, Kristensen & Cesari, 2016 {5 6 species + 1 subspecies}

Diaforobiotus caelicola (Kathman, 1990) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Stec *et al.* 2021a>

Diaforobiotus hyperonyx (Maucci, 1983) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* to *Tenuibiotus* by Pilato & Lisi 2011; Transferred from *Tenuibiotus* and amended by Stec & Morek 2022 based on type material and topotypic population>

Diaforobiotus islandicus islandicus (Richters, 1904) [*Macrobiotus ruffoi* Maucci, 1973] <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2016; Redescribed and neotype (from Grindavík, Iceland) designated by Stec 2023 (original type locality Faskends-Fjörd, eastern Iceland)>

Diaforobiotus islandicus nicaraguensis (Séméria, 1985) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Guidetti *et al.* 2016> {*nomen inquirendum* according to Stec 2023}

Diaforobiotus occidentalis (Murray, 1910) <Transferred from *Macrobiotus* by Massa *et al.* 2024>

Diaforobiotus quetzalcoatli Flores-Romero, López-Sandoval, Vincenzi, Cesari, Guidetti, Dueñas-Cedillo, Ruiz & Armendariz-Toledano, 2025

Diaporobiotus svalbardicus Stec, 2023

Richtersius Pilato & Binda, 1989 {6 species}

[*Richtersia* Pilato & Binda, 1987]

<Transferred from *Macrobotidae* by Guidetti *et al.* 2016>

Richtersius coronifer (Richters, 1903) <Redescribed by Stec *et al.* 2020a; neotype (from one of the original type locality Klaas Billen Bay, Svalbard, Norway) designated by Stec & Michalczyk 2020>

Richtersius ingemari Vecchi, Godziek, Kristensen, Piemontese, Calhim & Stec, 2025

Richtersius mazepi Kiosya & Stec, 2022

Richtersius nicolai Vecchi, Godziek, Kristensen, Piemontese, Calhim & Stec, 2025

Richtersius tertius Pogwizd & Stec, 2022

Richtersius ziemowiti Kayastha, Berdi, Miaduchowska, Gawlak, Łukasiewicz, Gołdyn, Jędrzejewski & Kaczmarek, 2020

Incertae sedis

{The placement of the following taxon into any superfamily remains still unclear, see Marley *et al.* 2011}

Family: Necopinatidae Ramazzotti & Maucci, 1983 {1 genus}

Necopinatum Pilato, 1971 {1 species}

Necopinatum mirabile Pilato, 1971

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